

Semantic Conflation Patterns of Motion Events in Vietnamese: Cognitive and Typological Perspectives

Ly Ngoc Toan

Ho Chi Minh City University of Law, Vietnam

This study examines how Vietnamese motion events conflate semantic components in verb roots, and serial-verb constructions in light of Talmy's and Slobin's typological predictions. This study employed a qualitative, typologically guided analysis, and it was supported by descriptive frequency counts. The data were compiled from two dictionaries and seventeen online stories, which produced 119 manner-motion verbs, 250 path-motion verbs, 265 cause-motion verbs, and 300 contextual tokens. The results show that Vietnamese encodes core internal components, namely Manner, Path, Cause, and a limited range of Figure and Ground in verb roots, whereas external components such as Direction, Result, Circumstance, Purpose, Sound, Vehicle, State, Change, and Co-motion are expressed through verb phrases and serial verb constructions. These distributions point to a stable hybrid profile in Vietnamese that combines verb-internal packaging with expansion at the level of constructions. The study provides a more precise refinement of motion-event typology for Vietnamese and offers implications for language teaching, translation practice, and natural language processing applications.

Keywords: *semantic conflation patterns, motion events, lexicalization patterns, construction grammar*

1 Introduction

Motion is one of the most fundamental domains of human cognition and experience, and it is encoded across languages in a pervasive manner, but languages encode it in different ways. Talmy (1985, 2000) builds on this insight and conceptualizes motion encoding through the notion of a motion event that consists of four semantic components, namely Figure, Ground, Manner, and Path. The Figure is the entity that moves or is located. The Ground is the entity that provides the reference frame for the Figure's location or trajectory. The Manner specifies how motion is carried out. The Path specifies the course or direction of motion. Talmy also proposes that Manner and Cause can function as co events, and these co-events elaborate how motion occurs or why motion occurs. Aske (1989) analyzes Spanish and shows that the Path component in a verb-framed language is lexicalized in the main verb. This lexicalization pattern restricts the overt encoding of Manner in the main verb. However, other semantic components, such as Circumstance or Causation, may still be expressed outside the main verb, and Figure 1 schematizes this distribution.

Figure 1: An expanded motion event (Aske 1989: 1)

Cross-linguistic contrasts in motion event can be illustrated by four examples below. In satellite-framed languages such as English, Manner is lexicalized in the main verb (*to run*) and Path is expressed in a satellite, namely preposition or particle (*into*).

- (1) The boy **ran into** the house.

In this example, *to run* encodes Manner and *into* encodes Path. In verb-framed languages such as French and Spanish, Path tends to be lexicalized in the main verb; whereas, Manner is expressed peripherally or omitted.

- (2) Le garçon est **entré dans** la maison.
The boy auxiliary enter into the house
'The boy entered the house.'

Serial-verb languages like Chinese often encode both Manner and Path in two verbs in a construction:

- (3) Nán hái **pǎo jìn** wū lǐ (男孩跑进屋里)
The boy ran enter house inside
'The boy ran into the house.'

Similarly, Vietnamese allows the combination of a Manner verb (*chạy*) and a Path verb (*vào*) in a serial-verb construction:

- (4) Anh ấy **chạy vào** nhà.
He run enter house
'He ran into the house.'

In example (4), the first verb *chạy* lexicalizes Manner and the second verb *vào* lexicalizes Path. Therefore, these two verbs are contiguous, and they share the same Figure and form one macro event. Since Talmy's (1985, 2000) distinction between satellite-framed languages and verb-framed languages has been refined, a range of typologists and cognitive linguists have identified additional channels through which motion components can be encoded. Ibarretxe Antuñano (2025) and Van Hoey (2025) show that ideophones and literary motion expressions can function as independent channels for encoding Manner and Path, and their findings extend motion typology beyond the original divide between verbs and satellites. Slobin (2004) introduces a third type that he calls equipollently-framed languages, and in this type Manner and Path are encoded through two verbal elements rather than through a main verb with a satellite. This pattern is prominent in serial verb constructions that are attested in many Southeast Asian languages and many West African languages. In this expanded typology, Vietnamese is considered an equipollently-framed language because Vietnamese speakers encode Manner and Path by combining two verbs in serial verb constructions. Moreover, Bohnemeyer et al. (2022) show that the ways speakers use reference frames and encode motion differ markedly from one community to another. This variation across communities

underscores the need for language-specific analyses that are firmly grounded in a coherent and well-defined theoretical framework.

Research on motion encoding in Vietnamese has attracted myriad attention from typological and cognitive perspectives. Early studies, such as Nguyễn Lai (2001), focus on directional verbs and their inherent motion meanings, and they provide a semantic inventory of Path that is related to lexical resources in Vietnamese. Subsequent work, including Mai Thị Thu Hân (2011), compares English and Vietnamese lexicalization patterns in order to situate Vietnamese in Talmy's motion typology while Hoàng Tuyết Minh (2016) further highlights the prominence of Path in Vietnamese motion verbs. More recent studies expand the scope beyond Path verbs alone. Lưu Quý Khương and Lý Ngọc Toàn (2018) document semantic and distributional differences among manner verbs, and Lý Ngọc Toàn (2019, 2022) extends the discussion to path-motion events and cause-motion events. At the constructional level, Dương Hữu Biên (2023) examines fictive motion in Vietnamese, and Võ Từ Phương (2025) argues that Vietnamese speakers frequently encode Manner and Path together in serial verb constructions, as illustrated in example (4). In short, these studies show that Vietnamese encodes motion through a combination of lexical resources, especially Path oriented verbs, and constructional resources, especially serial verb constructions, but they also suggest that an account of how these resources interact in a theoretical framework is still needed.

Although several studies have addressed this topic, a key gap remains. Previous studies have not provided a systematic account in a coherent theoretical framework of how motion semantic components are conflated in Vietnamese across verb roots and serial verb constructions. These studies have also not explicitly and systematically situated Vietnamese conflation patterns with respect to the typological predictions proposed by Talmy and by Slobin. Moreover, though these studies draw on cognitive and typological linguistics, they usually concentrate on individual components, such as the prominence of Path or variation in Manner, rather than on the overall distribution of motion components across lexical packaging and constructional packaging. The present study addresses this gap through a language investigation of motion expressions in Vietnamese. The study adopts a typological interpretive perspective because Vietnamese patterns are evaluated against verb-framed, satellite-framed, and equipollently-framed profiles, but the study does not analyze parallel data from non-Vietnamese languages.

The central notion in this study is semantic conflation. In Talmy's (1985, 2000) framework, semantic conflation refers to the integration of multiple semantic components of a motion event into a lexical unit or into a constructional unit. Following Talmy's definition, the present study uses the term semantic conflation to describe how Vietnamese speakers integrate motion components in verb roots and also integrate motion components in larger verb phrase structures, including serial verb constructions. The study examines this integration in order to clarify the distribution of motion components across lexical resources and constructional resources in Vietnamese. Based on this objective, the study addresses the following research questions.

- RQ1. How are internal components conflated in Vietnamese motion verbs, and what internal conflation patterns emerge across verb classes?
- RQ2. How do Vietnamese motion verbs combine with external components in verb phrases and serial-verb constructions, and what recurrent external conflation patterns are observed?

RQ3. How do the distributions of internal and external conflation situate Vietnamese in Talmy’s and Slobin’s typological predictions?

To answer these questions, the study conducts two models of semantic conflation. Internal conflation refers to cases in which one or more motion event components that are semantically entailed by the verb root are integrated into that verb root, as Figure 2a illustrates. External conflation refers to cases in which motion event components that are not semantically entailed by the verb root are contributed by adjacent elements in a verb phrase, and this contribution often takes the form of serial verb constructions, as Figure 2b illustrates. In this study, the labels internal components and external components are defined on the basis of Talmy’s motion event decomposition and Levin and Rappaport Hovav’s event structure model. Internal components include Manner, Path, and Cause because these components can be encoded in Vietnamese verb roots. In addition, Vietnamese motion verbs may incorporate Figure or Ground in lexical items, and these cases will be considered instances of internal conflation. External components include semantic components that are not entailed by the verb root and that extend the motion event through elements adjacent to the verb root. These components include Change, Circumstance, Co-motion, Direction, Intensifier, Purpose, Sound, State, and Vehicle. The study treats them as external because they are contributed by separate syntactic units, such as adverbs, particles, and additional verbs that participate in serial verb constructions.

Figure 2a: Internal conflation

Figure 2b: External conflation

On this basis, Talmy’s (1985, 2000) motion event framework provides the semantic inventory and the coding criteria for distinguishing internal conflation from external conflation. Slobin’s (2004) equipollently-framed hypothesis guides the analysis of serial verb constructions as elements that contribute to the encoding of Manner and Path. Goldberg’s (1995, 2006) construction grammar offers a model of how Vietnamese forms complex motion events through conventionalized pairings between form and meaning, and this model is relevant to cases of external conflation. Levin and Rappaport Hovav’s (1995, 1998, 2010) event structure model underpins the mapping between semantic components and event templates, and it also supports the distinction in this study between components that are entailed by the verb root and components that are supplied by peripheral elements. Figure 3 summarizes this analytic

framework by showing that Vietnamese allows internal conflation that parallels English verbs that conflate Manner, and it also allows external conflation that aligns with verb-framed patterns in French and Spanish, most clearly in serial verb constructions. In short, the internal and external conflation patterns simultaneously clarify how Vietnamese distributes motion event components between internal conflation of verbs and peripheral constructional components, and this distribution occurs while Vietnamese verbs remain morphologically simple.

Figure 3: Event structures of semantic conflation

2 Methodology

2.1 Research design

The study implements two models of semantic conflation: *internal conflation* and *external conflation* that are distinguished by whether motion-event components are semantically entailed by the verb root or supplied by peripheral elements. The research design is primarily qualitative and interpretive that is supported by quantitative counts and distributional comparisons. It comprises two components. The first is a lemma inventory of Vietnamese motion verbs that are compiled from major dictionaries. The second is a contextual analysis of motion-verb tokens that are extracted from the selected stories. The lemma inventory addresses RQ1, whereas the token-based analysis addresses RQ2 and RQ3.

Internal components and external components are adopted as analytical labels, grounded in Talmy’s motion-event framework and Levin and Rappaport Hovav’s event structure mapping. Each token is decomposed into these components. Internal components include Manner, Path, Cause, Figure, and Ground, because they may be entailed and encoded in Vietnamese verb roots. External components include Change, Circumstance, Co-motion, Direction, Emotion, Intensifier, Place/Location, Purpose, Result, Sound, State, Time, and Vehicle because they are not entailed by the verb root and extend the motion event through

adjacent elements. Vietnamese conflation patterns are interpreted with reference to the satellite-framed, verb-framed, and equipollently-framed profiles in linguistic typology.

Internal conflation occurs when one or more internal components are encoded in the verb root. External conflation occurs when the root encodes the motion element while one or more external components are contributed by adjacent elements within the verb phrase (e.g. secondary verbs, directional particles, adverbs, ideophones, or NPs). For example, in *đi chợ* ‘to go to the market’, *chợ* ‘market’ contributes an external Place component; in *bắn hạ* ‘to shoot down’, *hạ* ‘down’ contributes an external Result component. Serial verb constructions involve two or more verbs sharing the same subject, with each verb contributing a distinct component; typically, the first verb encodes Manner and the second encodes Path, as in *chạy vào* ‘to run into’, where *chạy* ‘to run’ encodes Manner and *vào* ‘into’ encodes Path. These verbs are coded separately to evaluate Slobin’s typological predictions.

In terms of procedure, first, motion verbs are identified in each sentence, then each token is coded for the presence of internal and external components. Tokens are labeled as instances of internal or external conflation and tabulated for descriptive comparison. Table 1 presents the coding categories and decision rules, explicitly linked to the theoretical framework to ensure analytic transparency.

2.2 Data collection

Data were collected to examine Vietnamese internal and external conflation at both lemma and token levels from two sources. The lemma dataset comes from two major dictionaries (Quang Hùng & Khắc Lâm 2007; Hoàng Phê 2020). The token dataset comes from seventeen stories on *truyenfull.vn* (Appendix A). These stories portray rural daily life, social conflict, and psychological hardship; thus, they provide frequent and concrete descriptions of bodily motion and cause-motion events. The selection keeps author, historical period, and narrative style relatively constant, which reduce genre/register effects on motion encoding.

From the dictionaries, motion-verb lemmas were compiled to build a type inventory. The final inventory includes 119 manner lemmas, 250 path lemmas, and 265 cause-motion lemmas. Only lemmas whose primary sense denotes physical motion were retained; near-duplicate synonyms were merged when justified by dictionary definitions, and obsolete or highly technical verbs were excluded. Each lemma was assigned to a semantic class and analyzed for entailed internal components in its definition. For example, *đẩy* ‘to push’ was classified as a cause-motion lemma that entails Cause, Motion, and Path; therefore, they exemplify internal conflation at the type level. These components were used to establish lemma-level patterns in the findings.

In parallel, token data were extracted from the seventeen stories. Each story was read sentence by sentence to identify motion verbs. A token was included if its lemma belongs to the dictionary inventory and its contextual use denotes physical displacement of a Figure; metaphorical or highly abstract uses (e.g. institutional progress) were excluded. Serial verb constructions and larger verb phrases were included whenever at least one element met the motion criteria; each motion verb in these complexes was coded for its own class and conflation pattern in the same sentential context. After exclusions, the corpus contains 420 sentences, of which 300 include at least one motion-verb token.

A lemma is a dictionary headword that represents a verb type, whereas a token is an attested contextual occurrence. Lemma counts describe type coverage across the three

inventories, while token counts support descriptive distributional comparison. Each token was annotated for surface form, lemma identity, semantic class, internal components, and external components. Table 1 summarizes the coding categories and annotation decisions.

Table 1: Coding rules

Category	What it codes	Decision rule	Example
MANNER internal	How motion occurs	Verb alone entails manner	<i>chạy</i> (to run), <i>bò</i> (to crawl)
PATH internal	Trajectory / direction	Verb alone entails path	<i>vào</i> (to enter), <i>ra</i> (to exit), <i>qua</i> (to cross)
CAUSE internal	Causing subevent	Verb entails agent-caused motion	<i>đẩy</i> (to push), <i>ném</i> (to throw), <i>bắn</i> (to shoot)
External components	Added outside V ₁	Meaning not entailed by V ₁ but contributed by V ₂ /particle/ adverb/ ideophone/ NP	Direction: <i>chạy vào</i> ; Result: <i>bắn hạ</i> ; Circum/Sound/Place/Vehicle/ Time: peripheral elaborators
Internal conflation (i)	Token label	Core M/P/C packaged in verb root; no independent external predicate	<i>Anh đẩy chiếc ghế.</i> He pushes the chair.
External conflation (e)	Token label	Any external component bonds with V ₁ to form complex predicate	<i>Anh ấy bắn hạ con chim.</i> He shot down the bird.

2.3 Data analysis

Data analysis is guided by Talmy’s motion-event framework, Slobin’s equipollently-framed hypothesis, and Goldberg’s construction grammar. Therefore, these perspectives provide the semantic inventory and typological expectations for coding and interpreting internal and external conflation. The analysis involves systematic coding of motion-verb tokens and descriptive comparison of internal and external conflation distributions across verb classes and component bundles. Each token was examined in context to identify the motion verb, determine associated components, and classify the token as internal or external conflation. A token was

coded as internal conflation when one or more components entailed by the verb root are integrated into that root; it was coded as external conflation when non-entailed components are supplied by adjacent elements such as particles, adverbs, or secondary verbs. For example, *Anh ấy chạy* instantiates internal conflation because *chạy* entails Manner, whereas *Anh ấy chạy qua hàng rào* exemplifies external conflation because *qua* adds Path outside the root.

The 300 tokens were analyzed in three stages. First, each sentence was scanned to identify motion verbs and annotate present internal/external components. Second, each token was assigned to a semantic class (Manner, Path, Cause) and labeled as internal or external conflation. Third, internal/external distributions were cross-tabulated by verb class and component bundles, and the tendencies were interpreted with reference to the three theoretical frameworks.

To maintain labeling consistency, fine-grained attributes from dictionary definitions and contexts were normalized into macro-features (e.g. fast, maximum speed, urgent → Speed; steady/regular pace → Pace regularity; forceful, violent → Force intensity). Micro-labels were retained only in illustrative examples. All descriptive counts and distributional patterns are based on macro-features, reducing annotator drift and enabling systematic comparisons. Coding was conducted in two passes. In the first pass, all tokens were annotated following Table 1. Then, interval, the dataset was re-checked in a second pass, focusing on borderline cases (e.g. purposive vs. locative complements and serial complexes). Disagreements were resolved by returning to dictionary definitions and contextual evidence, and recurring ambiguous cases were used to refine the operational rules before final tabulation. Tokens that remained non-motion or irreducibly ambiguous were excluded. This verification helps reduce annotator drift and supports stable distributional generalisations.

3 Findings and discussion

3.1 VERB [CAUSE MOTION]

This section examines semantic conflation patterns in Vietnamese cause-motion verbs, which denote events where an agent causes a Figure to move. The analysis focuses on how motion-event components are integrated into verb roots and into larger verb phrases. Following Talmy’s motion event framework and Goldberg’s construction grammar, the study distinguishes two types of conflation. Internal conflation occurs when the verb root encodes Cause together with at least one other core component, such as Figure, Manner, or Path so that the verb inherently evokes a cause-motion event. External conflation occurs when a cause-motion verb combines with peripheral elements in the verb phrase, especially in serial verb constructions, and these elements contribute additional components such as Result, Direction, Change, Intensifier, or State. Table 2 summarizes three internal conflation patterns and five external conflation patterns for Vietnamese cause motion verbs, and it shows that core meanings are often compressed in the verb root while peripheral meanings are expanded through constructions.

Table 2: Semantic conflation patterns of cause-motion verbs

Semantic components	Internal conflation patterns	External conflation patterns
	Internal components	External components

Semantic conflation patterns	Cause, Figure, Manner, Path				Change, Path, Result, State			
	Cause + Figure	Cause + Manner	Cause + Path	Cause + Result	Cause + Result + Intensifier	Cause + Result + Direction	Cause + Change	Cause + State
	8	27	30	67	20	49	44	20
Total	65				200			

3.1.1 Internal conflation patterns of cause-motion verbs

After analyzing 65 cause-motion verbs in Vietnamese, the findings show that these verbs conflate internal semantic components in three patterns, namely: $V_{[C+F]}$ (8), $V_{[C+M]}$ (27), and $V_{[C+P]}$ (30). These patterns are generalized in the pattern as follows:

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{CAUSE MOTION}]} = [\text{x CAUSE}_{(i)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{Inter-coms} \rangle]]$$

In this schema, x represents the causer role, and CAUSE(i) represents a cause-motion event whose core participants and subevents are lexically conflated into the verb. The term $\langle \text{Inter-coms} \rangle$ refers to the internal semantic components that are conflated into the verb root, including Cause (C), Figure (F), Manner (M), and Path (P). Therefore, the schema reflects the claim that Vietnamese cause-motion verbs encode a causative displacement template, in which the causer role and one or more internal components are co-lexicalized, and this co-lexicalization gives rise to the three internal conflation patterns identified in the data.

To begin with, when the internal components such as (C) and (F) are conflated into the cause-motion verbs, they establish the internal conflation pattern of $V_{[C+F]}$. This pattern shows that Vietnamese speakers simultaneously encode these internal components of a cause-motion event in a lexical structure.

$$V_{[C+F]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(i)} [\text{F (default) MOVES}]]$$

In this pattern, (C) denotes the causer that initiates the event, and the verb root inherently profiles a force or agentive source. (F) is encoded as a default affected entity that is conceptually required by the verb for the event to be interpretable, even when (F) is not overtly realized. In this study, any directional or manner implications that are inseparable from such default Figures are treated as part of (F) rather than as independent (M) or (P) in this pattern. Verbs such as *phà* ‘to blow’, *vắt* ‘to squeeze’, and *bắn* ‘to shoot’ illustrate this pattern because each verb entails an initiating force and a specific default Figure that undergoes displacement.

$$\begin{aligned} \textit{Phà} &\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(i)} [\text{F (default smoke/steam) MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{outward} \rangle]] \\ \textit{Vắt} &\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(i)} [\text{F (default water) MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{outward by squeezing} \rangle]] \\ \textit{Bắn} &\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(i)} [\text{F bullet/projectile MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{forward with force} \rangle]] \end{aligned}$$

The group of $V_{[C+F]}$ cause-motion verbs, whose lexical semantics already encode a causative displacement with two internal components. The verb root specifies (C) in the sense that it profiles an initiator that brings about an event. Therefore, the verb requires an external causer

argument to saturate this role in syntax or discourse. The verb root also specifies ⟨F⟩ in the sense that it presupposes a particular type of Figure as a default participant, even when that ⟨F⟩ is not overtly realized. Consequently, these verbs allow Vietnamese speakers to express a full CAUSE_(i) event in a compact way because ⟨C⟩ and ⟨F⟩ are already lexicalized in the verb. Though the verb can remain minimal while it still is semantically interpretable as a cause-motion event. The internal conflation is observed in the following example from *Rừng Xà Nu* (Nguyễn Trung Thành)

- (5) Chúng nó **bắn**.
they it shoot.
‘They shoot.’

In the clause *Chúng nó bắn*, the subject *chúng nó* corresponds to x, and x performs the causal initiation encoded by ⟨C⟩ in the verb *bắn*. The verb *bắn* also encodes ⟨F⟩ as a default projectile Figure. Therefore, even without an overt object, *bắn* still represents the CAUSE_(i) pattern in V_[C+F] because the verb root supplies both ⟨C⟩ and ⟨F⟩ while the syntax externalizes only x and leaves ⟨F⟩ to be recovered from the lexical meaning of the verb.

Second, the V_[C+M] is an internal conflation pattern that reflects how Vietnamese speakers can wrap the internal component of causer with two distinct manner components in a verb by capturing complex properties in one structure.

$$V_{[C+M]} \Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle M \rangle]]$$

This pattern denotes a CAUSE_(i) event, in which ⟨C⟩ and ⟨M⟩ are co lexicalized in the verb root. The verb profiles a force that brings about the displacement of ⟨F⟩, and it simultaneously specifies ⟨M⟩ as an internal component rather than as a modifier contributed by peripheral material. As a result, verbs that exemplify V_[C+M] encode a dual manner profile in which two tightly linked manner properties jointly characterize how the caused displacement unfolds. In this study, any directionally or positionally constrained implications that are inseparable from the manner of causation are considered part of ⟨M⟩ in this pattern. Verbs such as *ném* ‘to throw’, *quật* ‘to strike or slam’, *vác* ‘to carry, and *đá* ‘to kick’ illustrate V_[C+M] because each verb integrates the causative force with paired manner properties that are integral to the verb’s lexical meaning.

<i>Đá</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE}_{\langle \text{forceful} \rangle} \wedge \langle \text{directed-impact} \rangle]]$
<i>Ném</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE}_{\langle \text{forceful} \rangle} \wedge \langle \text{forward-trajectory} \rangle]]$
<i>Quật</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE}_{\langle \text{forceful} \rangle} \wedge \langle \text{downward-arc} \rangle]]$
<i>Vác</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE}_{\langle \text{carried} \rangle} \wedge \langle \text{on-shoulder} \rangle]]$

This group of V_[C+M] cause motion verbs includes verbs whose lexical semantics encode a causer role together with a manner component that contains two co occurring manner features, and these features are integral to the causative displacement event. The verb root encodes ⟨C⟩ because it profiles a force or an agentive source that brings the event about; therefore, the verb selects an external causer argument in syntax or in discourse. The verb root also encodes ⟨M⟩ because it wraps two non-neutral manner features in its internal event template. In *đá*, ⟨M⟩ combines forceful action with impact direction. In *ném*, ⟨M⟩ combines forceful action with a

forward trajectory. In *quật*, ⟨M⟩ combines forceful action with a downward arc. In *vác*, ⟨M⟩ combines carrying action with an on-shoulder body configuration. In this pattern, trajectory or posture implications that are inseparable from the manner of causation are treated as part of ⟨M⟩. Accordingly, these verbs differ from cause motion verbs with only one manner feature because their manner specification is not supplied by adverbials or by secondary verbs. The manner specification is conceptually obligatory and recoverable from the verb even in clauses that lack peripheral modifiers. The internal conflation is illustrated by the following tokens from *Chí Phèo* (Nam Cao).

- (6) Năm Thọ **vác** dao xộc vào.
 Nam Tho carry knife rush enter
 ‘Năm Thọ carried a knife and rushed.’

In this pattern, x is realized by *Năm Thọ* because *Năm Thọ* is the subject that triggers and controls the action denoted by *vác*. The verb *vác* encodes ⟨C⟩ because it profiles a force produced by x, and this force causes ⟨F⟩ to move, with ⟨F⟩ realized by *dao* in the sentence. The verb *vác* also encodes ⟨M⟩ because its lexical meaning specifies a carrying manner that is canonically shoulder carrying. Hence, this example reflects $V_{[C+M]}$ because *vác* bundles ⟨C⟩ and ⟨M⟩ into one verb root while the sentence supplies x and an overt ⟨F⟩ that goes through displacement under the encoded force and manner.

Third, the $V_{[C+P]}$ pattern refers to an internal semantic conflation, in which ⟨C⟩ and ⟨P⟩ are integrated in a verb itself. In this pattern, ⟨C⟩ functions as the causative force component that is encoded in the verb to start and sustain the displacement, whereas ⟨P⟩ functions as the path component that is also encoded in the verb to specify the direction or trajectory that constrains the displacement event.

$$V_{[C+P]} \Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle P \rangle]]$$

This pattern denotes a cause-motion event $\text{CAUSE}_{(i)}$, in which ⟨C⟩ and ⟨P⟩ are co-lexicalized in the verb root. The verb encodes ⟨C⟩ as a causative force that brings about displacement, and it encodes ⟨P⟩ as an inherent path value that specifies a non-neutral spatial direction, trajectory, or endpoint of motion. Therefore, a verb articulates $V_{[C+P]}$ when its lexical meaning simultaneously profiles causative force and fixes the directionality of the caused displacement. Vietnamese verbs such as *đẩy* ‘to push’, *nâng* ‘to lift or raise’, *ấn* ‘to press’, and *chèn* ‘to wedge’ exemplify this pattern because each verb encodes ⟨C⟩ and an inherent ⟨P⟩ within one lexical unit.

<i>Đẩy</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{forward} \rangle]]$
<i>Nâng</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{upward} \rangle]]$
<i>Ấn</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{downward} \rangle]]$
<i>Chèn</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(i)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{into} \rangle]]$

This group of $V_{[C+P]}$ cause-motion verbs includes verbs whose lexical semantics co-lexicalize ⟨C⟩ and ⟨P⟩, and both components are integral to the causative displacement event. The verb root encodes ⟨C⟩ because it profiles a causative force that acts on a Figure and produces displacement so that the event is interpreted as initiated by force rather than launched by the

Figure alone. The verb root also encodes ⟨P⟩ because it boxes a non-neutral directional value in its internal event template so that displacement is directed forward in *đẩy*, directed upward in *nâng*, directed downward in *ấn*, and directed into in *chèn*. Therefore, these verbs differ from causative verbs without inherent ⟨P⟩ because the directional specification is conceptually obligatory and recoverable from the verb root in every instantiation of $V_{[C+P]}$. This pattern is illustrated by the following tokens from *Chí Phèo* (Nam Cao).

- (7) Hãy ngấm ngấm **đẩy** người ta xuống sông.
let secretly push person that descend river
'Let us secretly push that person down into the river.'

In this token, the verb *đẩy* represents the $V_{[C+P]}$ pattern because it lexically encodes ⟨C⟩ as an exerted causative force and lexically encodes ⟨P⟩ as a path directed forward. The component ⟨C⟩ is entailed by *đẩy* because the verb profiles a force produced by x that acts on ⟨F⟩ and causes displacement. The component ⟨P⟩ is also entailed by *đẩy* because the verb constrains the displacement to proceed forward away from the force source. The phrase *xuống sông* contributes a specific endpoint and a downward orientation, but it does not replace the verb internal forward direction that is already encoded in *đẩy*. Therefore, the token matches the $V_{[C+P]}$ formula because the verb supplies both ⟨C⟩ and ⟨P⟩ within one verb root.

From the analysis of three internal conflation patterns, namely $V_{[C+F]}$, $V_{[C+M]}$, and $V_{[C+P]}$, the findings show that each pattern selects a different group of internal components, but all three patterns assign the verb root a central role in encoding causative initiation and displacement. As a result, the causing event, the participant, and the manner or direction of displacement are recoverable from the verb without necessarily requiring a separate resultative or directional complement. The three patterns differ in their internal loads because $V_{[C+F]}$ encodes a default Figure, $V_{[C+M]}$ encodes a dual Manner profile, and $V_{[C+P]}$ encodes an inherent Path.

This distribution connects with Talmy's typology because $V_{[C+P]}$ is verb framed in the sense that Path resides in the verb while $V_{[C+F]}$ and $V_{[C+M]}$ prioritize non-Path internal components but still keep the verb as the main locus of cause-motion meaning. From a construction grammar perspective, each cause-motion verb functions as a self-sufficient form meaning construction that satisfies the cause-motion frame at the lexical level, and external material typically refines telicity or trajectory rather than creating them from scratch. Event structure theory reflects the same result by considering these verbs as compact verbs that integrate a CAUSE subevent with a MOVE subevent, and that allow Figure, Manner, or Path to be internal semantic components.

Typologically, Vietnamese contrasts with several well-studied patterns of cause motion. Unlike English, which often splits cause-motion meaning between a verb and a satellite, and unlike Romance languages, which lexicalize Path in the verb while expressing goals with prepositions, Vietnamese integrates comparable meanings inside a single verb root. It also differs from Chinese, where resultative compounds are a common strategy. In Vietnamese, comparable semantic richness comes from morphologically simple, monomorphemic verbs, from which listeners can directly infer a default Figure, force initiation, and an inherent trajectory.

3.1.2 External conflation patterns of cause-motion verbs

This section examines external conflation in Vietnamese cause-motion event, namely the external integration of CAUSE(e) events. As Table 2 summarizes, Vietnamese not only compresses internal semantic components into verb roots, but also builds cause-motion meanings by combining a cause-motion verb with one or more external components. In CAUSE(e) patterns, the verb root supplies the internal core of causation and displacement while the external element contributes a peripheral component such as Result (R), Change (CH), or State (S), and Direction. Therefore, the section analyzes externally CAUSE(e) events, in which the outcome of displacement is not lexically entailed by the main verb itself, but is supplied by a secondary verb, a resultative adjective, a particle, or a prepositional element.

Two-component conflation patterns

The analysis of 131 cause-motion verbs identifies three recurrent external conflation patterns in Vietnamese, namely V_[C+R] (67), V_[C+CH] (44), and V_[C+S] (20), and all of these patterns follow the general schema

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{CAUSE MOTION}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge (\text{Exter-coms})]]$$

This schema articulates external conflation in Vietnamese caused-motion events and distinguishes two-component patterns and three-component patterns. In the schema, x is the causer, CAUSE(e) is the external causative event, (F) is the Figure, and MOVE is the motion element that is encoded by the main verb. In two component patterns, the main verb encodes causation and displacement, and an external component supplies an outcome component, so that the event is interpreted as cause and outcome, with the outcome contributed by (R), (CH), (S), or (V). In three-component patterns, one additional external specification is added, typically a result and a following directional or post result refinement so that the event is interpreted as causation that leads to displacement and culminates in a distinct resultant pattern. Across both types, the main verb encodes cause and motion that are linked to x, whereas (Exter-coms) is realized by a secondary verb, a particle, or a prepositional element, and this division of labor produces Vietnamese cause-motion macro-events.

The V_[C+R] pattern is the most frequent external conflation type of a cause-motion event in Vietnamese, which profiles a two-component event that links a causal action, a cause motion, and a result state as described in the schema below:

$$\text{V}_{[\text{C+R}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge (\text{result})]]$$

In this formula, x is the causer that launches the action, (F) is the Figure that is subjected to displacement, CAUSE(e) indexes the external causative event, MOVE is the motion element that is encoded by the main verb, and (R) is a resultant state contributed by an external element, typically a secondary verb in a serial verb construction. Therefore, the pattern bundles causation and displacement inside the main verb and adds a distinct result component outside the verb root. Because (R) specifies an endpoint state, the event is telic. In Vietnamese, (R) is commonly realized by a second verb, a particle, or a prepositional element. These two-component macro events are illustrated by expressions such as *đẩy ngã* ‘push down’, *ném vỡ* ‘throw and break’, *húc đổ* ‘ram down’, and *quật chết* ‘whip to death’.

$$\text{Đẩy ngã} \quad \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE}_{\langle \text{forward} \rangle} \wedge \langle \text{fall} \rangle]]$$

<i>Ném vỡ</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } \langle \text{forceful trajectory} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{break} \rangle]]$
<i>Húc đổ</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } \langle \text{impact} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{collapse} \rangle]]$
<i>Quật chết</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } \langle \text{violent} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{die} \rangle]]$

This verb group exemplifies the pattern by distributing semantic components across a serial verb construction. The main verb encodes the causal action and an internal manner specification that constrains how MOVE unfolds, such as $\langle \text{forward} \rangle$ in *đẩy*, $\langle \text{forceful trajectory} \rangle$ in *ném*, $\langle \text{impact} \rangle$ in *húc*, and $\langle \text{violent} \rangle$ in *quật*. The secondary verb supplies an entailed result state externally, namely $\langle \text{fall} \rangle$ in *ngã*, $\langle \text{break} \rangle$ in *vỡ*, $\langle \text{collapse} \rangle$ in *đổ*, and $\langle \text{die} \rangle$ in *chết*. Because $\langle R \rangle$ is contributed outside the main verb but remains in the same macro-event, the construction gives rise to a causative telic event, in which the causal subevent canonically culminates in the result state. This organization is illustrated in the following example from *Đông Trinh Ngải* (Nghiem Dieu Linh).

- (8) Chợt bị Hà **đẩy** **ngã**.
suddenly be Hà push fall.
‘I was suddenly pushed down by Hà.’

In this sentence, x is *Hà* as the causer and $\langle F \rangle$ is *tôi* as the displaced Figure. The verb *đẩy* encodes CAUSE(e) together with the internal manner implication $\langle \text{forward} \rangle$ and supplies MOVE while the secondary verb *ngã* supplies $\langle R \rangle$ as the entailed result $\langle \text{fall} \rangle$. Therefore, the serial verb construction *đẩy ngã* expresses a macro-event that combines causation, displacement, and attainment of the result state.

The $V_{[C+CH]}$ pattern is an external conflation type that extends a cause-motion verb by adding an explicit change-of-state endpoint, and this pattern is schematized as follows:

$$V_{[C+CH]} \Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } \wedge \langle \text{change} \rangle]]$$

In this pattern, the main verb supplies CAUSE(e) and MOVE while the change component $\langle CH \rangle$ is realized outside the verb root by a resultative adjectival element that specifies the transformation endpoint. Because $\langle CH \rangle$ is entailed by the verb adjective construction, the resulting event is telic. The adjectival outcome fixes a transformation endpoint, as in outcomes such as broken, flattened, curved, or crushed.

<i>Đạp gãy</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } [\langle \text{downward force} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{broken} \rangle]]]$
<i>Ép bẹp</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } [\langle \text{forceful forward} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{flattened} \rangle]]]$
<i>Bẻ cong</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } [\langle \text{forceful manipulation} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{curved} \rangle]]]$
<i>Đè giập</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE } [\langle \text{downward-pressure} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{crush/flatten} \rangle]]]$

This group of $V_{[C+CH]}$ cause-motion verbs consists of external verb phrases, in which the cause-motion verb supplies $\langle C \rangle$ and MOVE, and a resultative adjectival element supplies $\langle CH \rangle$ as a transformation endpoint. The verb root introduces the causal action that acts on $\langle F \rangle$ and triggers displacement while the adjective specifies the resultant state that is distinct from the motion element. Verb phrases such as *đạp gãy* ‘to break with a foot’, *ép bẹp* ‘to flatten by pressing’, *bẻ cong* ‘to bend’, and *đè giập* ‘to press down and crush’ exemplify this pattern because each phrase combines a causative motion verb with an adjectival result that encodes

⟨CH⟩ and yields a telic CAUSE(e) event. The V_[C+CH] external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Trên những con đường Việt Bắc* (Nam Cao).

- (9) Bị gọng sắt **đè** **giập** xương.
be iron-clamp press crush bone
'(He was) crushed to the bone by the iron clamp.'

In this example, the verb phrase *đè giập* is a verb-adjective construction. The verb *đè* encodes ⟨C⟩ as a downward causative pressure that acts on ⟨F⟩ and brings about displacement, which supplies MOVE in the CAUSE(e) event. The adjectival element *giập* encodes ⟨CH⟩ as the change into a crushed state, and this change endpoint makes the event telic. Therefore, the token is interpreted as a CAUSE(e) event, in which downward causation leads to displacement and culminates in a definite transformation that is supplied by the external adjectival component.

The V_[C+S] pattern augments a cause-motion verb with a stable post-event state rather than a structural transformation, and it is formalized as follows:

$$V_{[C+S]} \Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{state} \rangle]]$$

In this formula, ⟨S⟩ is a state endpoint contributed by an external complement, such as tight, closed, fixed, or rigid. The main verb supplies CAUSE(e) and MOVE while the complement adds a distinct state component outside the verb root. Because ⟨S⟩ specifies an endpoint that persists after culmination, the resulting event is telic. The state complement is typically realized by an adjective, a secondary verb, a prepositional element, or a particle, and it often implies completeness or tightness.

<i>Buộc chặt</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \langle \text{binding action} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{tightly bound} \rangle]]$
<i>Đóng kín</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \langle \text{closing action} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fully closed} \rangle]]$
<i>Mở toang</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \langle \text{opening action} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{wide open} \rangle]]$
<i>Đè cứng ngắt</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \langle \text{pressing action} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{rigid} \rangle]]$

This group of verb phrases consists of externally componentated verbs, in which the verb root encodes ⟨C⟩ as a causative force that brings about displacement, and the external element encodes ⟨S⟩ as a stable resultant condition that persists after the event. The state complement fixes a telic endpoint by specifying the persistent pattern that reaches at the end of displacement. Typical verb phrases illustrating this structure include *buộc chặt* 'to tie tightly', *đè cứng ngắt* 'to press until rigid', *đóng kín* 'to close completely', and *mở toang* 'to open wide' because each combines a causative motion verb with a state complement that gives rise to a post event state and foregrounds ⟨S⟩ rather than ⟨CH⟩. The V_[C+S] external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Điếu văn* (Nam Cao).

- (10) Tôi **đóng** **kín** cửa phòng.
I close tight door room.
'I closed the room door completely.'

In this pattern, *x* is realized by *tôi* as the causer. The verb *đóng* encodes ⟨C⟩ because it profiles a force produced by *x* that acts on ⟨F⟩, realized by *cửa phòng*, and brings about MOVE. The adjective *kín* encodes ⟨S⟩ by specifying the stable resultant state of being fully closed, and the combination *đóng* + *kín* forms the verb phrase *đóng kín* that packages the causative displacement element together with this post-event state. In short, this token expresses a telic CAUSE(e) event, in which causative force leads to displacement and culminates in a persistent state endpoint that is supplied by the external complement.

For the two-component external conflation patterns, the three Vietnamese patterns are manifested by the schema $\text{VERB}_{[\text{CAUSE MOTION}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{Exter-coms} \rangle]]$, in which the main verb encodes CAUSE(e) and MOVE, while an external complement supplies one endpoint, such as ⟨R⟩, ⟨CH⟩, ⟨S⟩, or an added manner value. This organization suggests an endpoint externalization strategy in Vietnamese, where telicity is tracked by the complement rather than by the verb root alone. The strategy resembles satellite-framed conflation with respect to telicity, but it extends Talmy’s satellite notion because Vietnamese endpoints are realized by particles and by adjectives, secondary verbs, and prepositional elements. In comparison with Romance languages and Chinese, Vietnamese maintains morphologically simple verb roots while it still allows a productive and semantically rich slot for external endpoints. Consequently, the two-component patterns support the view that endpoint externalization is a typological parameter that interacts with, but cannot be reduced to, the verb-framed and satellite-framed distinction in motion encoding.

Three-component conflation patterns

These patterns consist of 69 cause-motion verbs as summarized in Table 1, in which two external conflation patterns, namely $\text{V}_{[\text{C} + \text{R} + \text{I}]}$ (20), $\text{V}_{[\text{C} + \text{R} + \text{P}]}$ (49) are identified. These patterns follow the schema:

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{CAUSE MOTION}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{Exter-coms} \rangle]]$$

The first pattern, $\text{V}_{[\text{C} + \text{R} + \text{I}]}$, is schematized as:

$$\text{V}_{[\text{C} + \text{R} + \text{I}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{R} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{I} \rangle]]$$

This formula represents a CAUSE(e) event, in which *x* is the causer and ⟨C⟩ is the initiating force produced by *x* that triggers caused motion. ⟨R⟩ marks the final outcome brought about by that motion and functions as the result endpoint. ⟨I⟩ is an intensifier that applies after ⟨R⟩ and specifies the degree or salience of the attained result without introducing a new motion subevent. Therefore, the structure encodes three ordered components, namely ⟨C⟩, ⟨R⟩, and ⟨I⟩, and these components form one macro event of coherent multi phase while the main verb remains morphologically simple.

<i>Quạt ngã nhào</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{forceful} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fall} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{heavily} \rangle]]$
<i>Hất văng mạnh</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{upward} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fly away} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{strongly} \rangle]]$
<i>Xô đổ ập</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{push} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{collapse} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{suddenly} \rangle]]$
<i>Ném vỡ toang</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{x CAUSE}_{(e)} [\text{F MOVE} \wedge \langle \text{throw} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{break} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{loudly} \rangle]]$

This group of $\text{V}_{[\text{C} + \text{R} + \text{I}]}$ cause-motion verbs is realized as a verb serial construction of the form $\text{V1} + \text{V2} + \text{I}$, in which V1 encodes ⟨C⟩ as the causal action, V2 encodes ⟨R⟩ as the result

endpoint, and I encodes ⟨I⟩ as a degree specification that applies after ⟨R⟩ and is realized as an adjective or an adverb. Verb phrases such as *quật ngã nhào* ‘to strike down heavily’, *hất văng mạnh* ‘to jerk away forcefully’, *xô đổ ập* ‘to push over suddenly’, and *ném vỡ toang* ‘to throw and smash wide open’ represent this pattern because they integrate causative force, resultant displacement, and post result intensification into a telic macro event. The $V_{[C+R+I]}$ external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Mỹ Nhân Nhập Vai* (Hoắc Hương Cô).

- (11) Hấn **hất văng mạnh** chủ thủ trong tay nàng.
He toss fling strong dagger in hand she
‘He flung the dagger out of her hand forcefully.’

In this $V_{[C+R+I]}$ pattern, x is realized by *hấn* as the causer, and ⟨F⟩ is realized by *chủ thủ*. The verb *hất* encodes ⟨C⟩ by profiling the force exerted by x that sets ⟨F⟩ into displacement, while the verb *văng* encodes ⟨R⟩ by specifying the flung-away result endpoint. The adjective *mạnh* encodes ⟨I⟩ because it scales the attained ⟨R⟩ as a high degree of force and intensity in the post-result stage. Consequently, the token expresses a multi-phase CAUSE(e) macro-event, in which ⟨C⟩ launches motion, motion culminates in ⟨R⟩, and ⟨I⟩ further qualifies that result.

The second pattern, $V_{[C+R+D]}$ is formulated as follows:

$$V_{[C+R+D]} \Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge [\langle R \rangle \wedge \langle D \rangle]]]$$

This formula represents a CAUSE(e) macro event, in which x is the causer that initiates the causal action. ⟨R⟩ marks the resultant state brought about by the primary motion, and ⟨D⟩ specifies a directional or destination value that applies after ⟨R⟩ is achieved and refines the result phase. Therefore, this pattern encodes a three-component temporal sequence that consists of the cause, the resultant state ⟨R⟩, and the result directional specification ⟨D⟩, and these components integrate into one coherent multi phase event while the main verb remains morphologically simple.

<i>Đẩy ngã ra</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge [\langle \text{push} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fall} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{outwards} \rangle]]]$
<i>Xô đổ vào</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge [\langle \text{push} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{collapse} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{inwards} \rangle]]]$
<i>Hất văng lên</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge [\langle \text{upward} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fly away} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{upwards} \rangle]]]$
<i>Quật ngã xuống</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [x \text{ CAUSE}_{(e)} [F \text{ MOVE} \wedge [\langle \text{forceful} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{fall} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{downwards} \rangle]]]$

This group of $V_{[C+R+D]}$ cause-motion verbs is realized as macro serial verb constructions of the form V1 + V2 + V3, in which V1 encodes ⟨C⟩ as a causative force that sets the Figure into displacement, V2 encodes ⟨R⟩ as a resultant state, and V3 encodes ⟨D⟩ as a result directional value. Constructions such as *đẩy ngã ra* ‘to push and make fall outwards’, *xô đổ vào* ‘to push and cause to collapse inward’, *hất văng lên* ‘to fling and cause to fly upward’, and *quật ngã xuống* ‘to strike and cause to fall downward’ express this pattern because they integrate causation, an telic result, and a following directional specification into one macro event. The $V_{[C+R+D]}$ external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Trần Cừ* (Nam Cao).

- (12) Minh **đẩy** anh đội viên **ngã ra**.
Minh push male squad-member fall outwards.
‘Minh pushed the squad member so that he fell outward.’

In this example, *x* is realized by *Minh* and ⟨F⟩ is realized by *anh đội viên*. The verb *đẩy* encodes ⟨C⟩ as the pushing force that brings about displacement, the verb *ngã* encodes ⟨R⟩ as the bounded falling result endpoint, and the directional element *ra* encodes ⟨D⟩ as the outward destination that applies after ⟨R⟩ is achieved. Thus, the token *r* manifests a CAUSE(e) macro event that matches the $V_{[C+R+D]}$ formula.

For the three-component external conflation patterns, Vietnamese motivates a cautious hybrid characterization that bears on ongoing debates about motion-event typology. On the one hand, it patterns with verb-framed systems in that cause-motion verbs lexicalize the CAUSE-MOTION core and may encode non-neutral directionality in the root. On the other hand, Vietnamese regularly externalizes result-phase material in ordered three-component constructions: ⟨C⟩→⟨R⟩→⟨I/D⟩ through co-verbs, particles, or adjectives/ adverbs that produce a telic macro-event with multiple syntactically independent heads. This shows that Vietnamese is not satellite-framed in the English sense, nor straightforwardly verb-framed; rather, it exploits serial componenting depth and endpoint externalization as separable resources. Given critiques that question the ontological status of the verb and satellite dichotomy, the Vietnamese three-component patterns support a typology where culmination and post-culmination refinement are constructionally distributed, refining cross-linguistic models of event structure.

3.2 VERB _[MANNER MOTION]

This section examines semantic conflation patterns of manner motion verbs in Vietnamese, in which verbs encode Manner ⟨M⟩ together with other motion components. Two conflation types are identified. Internal conflation involves internal components, including Manner ⟨M⟩ and, in some verbs, Figure ⟨F⟩ or Ground ⟨G⟩, so that the verb root alone provides a self-sufficient motion event element. External conflation involves the combination of ⟨M⟩ with peripheral components, such as Sound ⟨S⟩, Circumstance ⟨C⟩, Vehicle ⟨V⟩, or Co-motion ⟨Co⟩, which are encoded by adjuncts or by additional verbs in serial verb constructions and expand the event at the verb phrase level. Table 2 summarizes these internal and external patterns with representative examples.

Table 3: Semantic conflation patterns of manner-motion verbs

Semantic components	Internal conflation patterns		External conflation patterns			
	Internal components (Figure, Manner)		External components (Circumstance, Sound, Purpose, Vehicle)			
	Manner + Figure	Manner + Sound	Manner + Circumstance	Manner + Purpose	Manner + Vehicle	Manner + Co-motion
Conflation patterns of manner verbs	19	28	19	21	17	15
Total	19			100		

3.2.1 Internal conflation patterns of manner-motion verbs

As shown in Table 2, these patterns belong to the group of two-component conflation. This is, these patterns involve internal semantic components (Inter-coms), such as Manner ⟨M⟩, and Figure ⟨F⟩, which are integrated into the main verbs. Moreover, these verbs encode the movement type and its qualitative features in the verb root, without relying on additional

morphological markers. There is a main pattern: $V_{[M+F]}$ with 19 verbs. The general event formula for internal conflation patterns of manner verbs is:

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{MANNER MOTION}]} = [F \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge \langle \text{Inter-coms} \rangle]$$

The first pattern, the $V_{[M+F]}$ pattern consists of two internal semantic components in a lexical unit, namely $\langle M \rangle$ and $\langle F \rangle$. This pattern is formalized as:

$$V_{[M+F]} \Leftrightarrow [F_{\langle \text{default} \rangle} \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge \langle M \rangle]$$

In this pattern, $\text{MOVE}_{(i)}$ denotes an internal manner-motion event. $\langle M \rangle$ refines the qualitative execution of the motion by specifying the characteristic mode of movement tied to the verb, and $\langle F_{\langle \text{default} \rangle} \rangle$ encodes a prototypical participant that is lexically presupposed by the verb. More particularly, $\langle F \rangle$ is not an argument slot to be filled syntactically, but a default selectional restriction embedded in the verb’s semantics, as in *bước* ‘to step’, *mưa* ‘to rain’, *gật* ‘to nod’, and *cúi* ‘to bend’.

<i>Bước</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F_{\langle \text{human} \rangle} \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [\langle \text{leg-based} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{measured} \rangle]]$
<i>Mưa</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F_{\langle \text{raindrops} \rangle} \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [\langle \text{fall} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{downward} \rangle]]$
<i>Gật</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F_{\langle \text{human head} \rangle} \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [\langle \text{bend} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{downward} \rangle]]$
<i>Cúi</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [F_{\langle \text{human upper body} \rangle} \text{ MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [\langle \text{bend} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{downward} \rangle]]$

This group of $V_{[M+F]}$ manner-motion verbs can be characterized as verbs whose lexical semantics obligatorily combines a $\langle F \rangle$ together with a $\langle M \rangle$ specification, and these two components jointly define $\text{MOVE}_{(i)}$. The verb root encodes $\langle F \rangle$ by selecting a conventional class, for instance $\langle \text{legs} \rangle$ in *bước*, $\langle \text{water/ raindrops} \rangle$ in *mưa*, $\langle \text{human head} \rangle$ in *gật*, and $\langle \text{human upper body} \rangle$ in *cúi*. The verb root encodes $\langle M \rangle$ by fixing the characteristic motion profile associated with that $\langle F \rangle$, for instance leg-based measured stepping in *bước*, water descending from above in *mưa*, downward bending of the head in *gật*, and downward bending of the upper body in *cúi*. Therefore, the $\langle F \rangle$ and the $\langle M \rangle$ are internally supported by the verb rather than supplied by external modifiers. The $V_{[M+F]}$ internal conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Mua nhà* (Nam Cao).

- (13) **Mưa** như những cái roi da quất xuống đầu.
rain like many female whip leather lash down head
‘The rain was like leather whips lashing down on (one’s) head.’

The $V_{[M+F]}$ pattern shows that the verb *mưa* lexically encodes ⟨F⟩ as default water, concretely raindrops, and it lexically encodes ⟨M⟩ as water moving downward from above in a falling or dripping profile. The simile in (13) intensifies the sensory impact of that downward water movement, but it does not introduce ⟨F⟩ or ⟨M⟩ because both components are already co-lexicalized in *mưa*. Therefore, the token exemplifies a complete MOVE(i) event, in which default water undergoes downward displacement with an internally specified manner profile.

In short, the internal conflation pattern $V_{[M+F]}$ reveals a strong lexical-compression strategy in Vietnamese manner-motion verbs. These patterns support Talmy’s view that ⟨M⟩ is a core component of manner-motion verbs because the internal event can be recovered from the verb root without an obligatory satellite or complement. At the same time, they challenge Talmy’s strict satellite-framed versus verb-framed split since Vietnamese can co-lexicalize ⟨M⟩ together with a ⟨F⟩ inside one monomorphemic verb. This level of internal integration makes Vietnamese typologically closer to equipollently-framed languages such as Thai and Chinese than to verb-framed Romance languages such as Spanish and French, which rarely encode default ⟨F⟩ in the verb and instead externalize such information. From a construction-grammar perspective, these verbs function as self-sufficient form-meaning constructions in which ⟨F⟩ are lexically presupposed selectional restrictions instead of peripheral adjuncts, so event-structure models like Levin and Rappaport Hovav’s must allow ⟨F⟩ to be internal components in some languages. Therefore, Vietnamese manner-motion verbs instantiate a high-integration internal conflation parameter that positions Vietnamese between verb-framed and equipollently-framed systems while they preserve the option of external expansion elsewhere.

3.2.2 External conflation patterns of manner-motion verbs

This section is involved in external conflation patterns of Vietnamese manner-motion verbs that belong to two-component patterns. In these patterns, the verbs encode manner ⟨M⟩ while additional external components (Exter-coms) such as Sound ⟨S⟩, Circumstance ⟨Ci⟩, Purpose ⟨Pr⟩, Vehicle ⟨V⟩, and Co-motion ⟨CO⟩ are expressed through peripheral lexical units as in $V_{[M+S]}$, $V_{[M+Ci]}$, $V_{[M+Pr]}$, $V_{[M+V]}$, and $V_{[M+CO]}$. These patterns reflect a general mechanism of core compression, peripheral expansion, in which the clause maintains a concise semantic element while they still remain open to flexible contextual elaboration. The general formula for these patterns can be represented as:

$$\text{VERB}_{[MANNER\ MOTION]} = [{}_F\text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [{}_{\langle\text{Exter-coms}\rangle}]]$$

In this formula, $\text{MOVE}_{(e)}$ is interpreted not merely as a general motion event, but specifically as an event of external manner motion, in which the motion and its manner are encoded together, and the external element functions as a distinct semantic component.

The first pattern is:

$$V_{[M+S]} \Leftrightarrow [{}_F\text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [{}_{\langle M \rangle \wedge \langle S \rangle}]]$$

This pattern combines a manner component ⟨M⟩ with an external sound component ⟨S⟩ to form a verb phrase of the type V+ adverb. In this formula, ⟨F⟩ is involved in displacement, MOVE(e) represents an event of external manner motion, ⟨M⟩ specifies how ⟨F⟩ moves, and ⟨S⟩ specifies the auditory impression that accompanies that movement. The sound is not inherent to the manner itself, but adds an extra perceptual component that heightens vividness. Vietnamese exploits this pattern with ideophones and reduplication to evoke multisensory motion in narrative discourse.

<i>Chạy rầm rập</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (fast) ∧ (rumbling)]]
<i>Đi lộp cộp</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (regular pace) ∧ (clattering)]]
<i>Bay vèo</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(airborne) ∧ (fast) ∧ (whizzing)]]
<i>Bò sột soạt</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(limb-based) ∧ (slow) ∧ (rustling)]]

This group of V_[M+S] manner-motion verbs can be characterized as expressive verb-adverb complexes, in which the verb root encodes ⟨M⟩ as the qualitative displacement profile of ⟨F⟩, and the sound adverb encodes ⟨S⟩ as a co-event temporally aligned with that displacement. Typical verb phrases include *chạy rầm rập* ‘to run noisily’, *đi lộp cộp* ‘to walk steadily with clattering sounds’, *bay vèo* ‘to fly quickly with a whizzing sound’, and *bò sột soạt* ‘to crawl slowly with rustling noise’. The contrast between *đi* as neutral walking and *chạy* as fast, high-energy running helps explain why different sound co-events pair with each verb. The V_[M+S] pattern is manifested in the following token from *Nước mắt* (Nam Cao).

- (14) Nên tờ giấy bạc **bay vèo**.
so banknote fly whizzing
‘So the banknote flew off with a whizzing sound.’

In this pattern, ⟨F⟩ is *tờ giấy bạc*, this ⟨F⟩ that is displaced. The verb *bay* encodes ⟨M⟩ by profiling an airborne, rapid flight manner of displacement of ⟨F⟩. The ideophone *vèo* encodes ⟨S⟩ by contributing a whizzing sound that accompanies the flight and intensifies its perceptual force through a morphological form of adverb. Therefore, the token realizes an external manner-motion event, in which ⟨F⟩ moves by a flight manner and the movement is rendered vivid by an aligned sound co-event.

The second pattern is shown as below:

$$V_{[M+C]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle M \rangle \wedge \langle C \rangle]]$$

This pattern bundles a manner component ⟨M⟩ with an external circumstance component ⟨C⟩ to form a verb phrase of the type V + adverb. In this pattern, ⟨F⟩ is the ⟨F⟩ that is subjected to displacement, MOVE(e) is an external manner-motion event encoded by the main verb, and ⟨C⟩ frames that motion in a situational, psychological, or attitudinal context. The circumstance component does not add a new motion element, but it shapes the pragmatic interpretation by conveying meanings such as aimlessness, urgency, timidity, or playful stance.

<i>Đi lang thang</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (aimless) ∧ (wander)]]
<i>Chạy thực mạng</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (fast) ∧ (escape)]]
<i>Đi khúm núm</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (timid) ∧ (submissive)]]

Nhảy non-ton ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (playful) ∧ (lively)]]

This group of V_[M+C] manner-motion verbs consists of expressive verb-adverb complexes, in which the verb root supplies the locomotion profile and manner of ⟨F⟩, while the adverbial element contributes ⟨C⟩ as an evaluative or contextual overlay. Verb phrases include *đi lang thang* (to wander aimlessly), *chạy thực mạng* ‘to run desperately’, *đi khúm núm* ‘to walk timidly or submissively’, and *nhảy non ton* ‘to jump playfully’ because each verb retains a stable manner core and adds a circumstance that signals speaker evaluation or participant attitude. The V_[M+C] pattern is represented in the following token from *Người làng Ner* (Ngọc Tấn).

- (15) Cô ấy **đi lang thang** rồi quên mất đường về.
she walk wander then forget lose road return
‘She wandered around and then forgot the way home.’

This example shows that ⟨F⟩ is *cô ấy*, the displaced ⟨F⟩. The verb *đi* encodes MOVE_(e) with a neutral leg-based manner ⟨M⟩. The adverbial *lang thang* encodes ⟨C⟩ by framing the walking as aimless and unfocused. Therefore, this sentence realizes a external manner-motion event, in which ⟨F⟩ moves by walking and the circumstance component fixes the event as wandering.

The third pattern is represented as follows:

V_[M+Pr] ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(M) ∧ (Pr)]]

This pattern encodes a manner component ⟨M⟩ together with an explicit purposive goal ⟨Pr⟩ to form a serial verb complex. In this case, MOVE_(e) denotes the externally construed manner-of-motion event encoded by the main verb, whereas ⟨Pr⟩ identifies the intended motion endpoint, the goal toward which the Figure’s displacement is directed. More specially, ⟨Pr⟩ in Vietnamese may be realized either as (i) a goal-action (e.g. *học* ‘to study’, *chợ* ‘shop/ market shopping’, *dịch* ‘relief work’ or (ii) a conventionalized destination noun that functions as an intended endpoint in fixed motion expressions (e.g. *nhà* ‘home’ in *về nhà*). The key property of this pattern is that Vietnamese keeps the motion verb and the purposive goal element syntactically independent while they share the same subject, as in *đi học* ‘go to study/school’, *đi chợ* ‘go shopping/market-going’, *chạy dịch* ‘to rush to relief work’, and *về nhà* ‘to return home’.

Đi học ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (regular pace) ∧ (study)]]
Chạy dịch ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (urgent) ∧ (do relief work)]]
Đi chợ ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (regular pace) ∧ (go shopping)]]
Về nhà ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (regular pace) ∧ (return-home)]]

This group of V_[M+Pr] manner-motion verbs can be characterized as serial complexes, in which the manner-motion verb profiles displacement with ⟨M⟩, and the subsequent element contributes ⟨Pr⟩ as an intended endpoint that completes a destination-/purpose-oriented interpretation. Therefore, they differ from manner-motion verbs, in which no purposive goal component is integrated into the verb phrase. The following token from *Nước mắt* (Nam Cao) exemplifies this pattern.

- (16) Mãi đến chiều mới về nhà mà không ăn thì đói.
only until afternoon then return home but not eat then hungry
‘Only in the afternoon did (they) return, and if (they) did not eat, (they) would be hungry.’

In this example, ⟨F⟩ is the understood returning participant (Figure). The verb *về* encodes MOVE(e) together with ⟨M⟩ as a return-movement profile. The following element *nhà* contributes ⟨Pr⟩ as an intended endpoint, which gives rise to a purposive/destination-oriented return event. Even when the endpoint is only contextually recoverable rather than overtly specified, the construction still licenses a goal-oriented reading in which the motion is construed as directed toward attaining that endpoint.

The V_[M+V] pattern is schematized as follows:

$$V_{[M+V]} \Leftrightarrow [{}_F \text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [{}_M \wedge \langle V \rangle]]$$

This pattern boxes a manner verb with an external vehicle component ⟨V⟩ to form a verb phrase of the type V + noun that specifies the means of transport. In this pattern, ⟨F⟩ refers to displacement, MOVE(e) is the external manner-motion event encoded by the main verb, ⟨M⟩ specifies the displacement profile, and ⟨V⟩ identifies the transport medium that enables the movement. Therefore, the vehicle is realized as an independent lexical item in Vietnamese, which supports productive and metaphorical extensions, as in *cưỡi ngựa* ‘to ride a horse’, *chèo thuyền* ‘to row a boat’, *lái xe* ‘to drive a car’, and *lướt ván* ‘to surf’.

<i>Cưỡi ngựa</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [{}_F \text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [{}_M \wedge \langle \text{ride} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{animal-based} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{horse} \rangle]]$
<i>Chèo thuyền</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [{}_F \text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [{}_M \wedge \langle \text{row} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{water-based} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{boat} \rangle]]$
<i>Lái xe</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [{}_F \text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [{}_M \wedge \langle \text{drive} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{vehicle-based} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{car} \rangle]]$
<i>Lướt ván</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [{}_F \text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [{}_M \wedge \langle \text{glide} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{surface-based} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{board} \rangle]]$

This group of V_[M+V] verbs consists of verb-noun complexes, in which the verb root encodes ⟨M⟩ as a specific transport-based manner, and the following noun encodes ⟨V⟩ as the concrete vehicle. The two components jointly produce one coherent external manner-motion event because the vehicle is conceptually required for interpreting how the ⟨F⟩ moves. The V_[M+V] pattern is described in the following token from *Truyện người hàng xóm* (Nam Cao).

- (17) Con gái không biết cưỡi ngựa ngồi không vững.
girl not know ride horse sit not firm
‘The girl did not know how to ride a horse, so she could not sit steadily.’

In this case, ⟨F⟩ is *con gái* that involved in the transport event. The verb *cưỡi* encodes MOVE(e) together with ⟨M⟩ by profiling a riding manner in which ⟨F⟩ is carried by and controls a mount. The noun *ngựa* encodes ⟨V⟩ by specifying the vehicle medium as a horse. Therefore, the token clarifies this pattern by combining a manner verb with an explicit vehicle noun to encode transport-based displacement.

Last but not least, the pattern V_[M+CO] is formulated as follows:

$$V_{[M+CO]} \Leftrightarrow [{}_F \text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [{}_M \wedge \langle \text{CO} \rangle]]$$

This pattern represents an external manner-motion event MOVE(e), in which ⟨F⟩ is associated with displacement. In this pattern, the verb root encodes ⟨M⟩ as the qualitative profile of that displacement, and the external component ⟨C_o⟩ contributes a co-motion component. The ⟨C_o⟩ confirms that another entity moves in coordination, accompaniment, or ordered sequence with ⟨F⟩, so it adds a social or interactive alignment to the same motion event. Although ⟨M⟩ and ⟨C_o⟩ remain syntactically independent in a verb-phrase construction, they integrate into a coherent macro event that depicts both locomotion and accompanying participation without altering the morphology of the main verb as in *đi theo* ‘to follow’, *chạy cùng* ‘to run together’, *nói đuôi* ‘to move in a line’, and *sánh đôi* ‘to walk side by side’.

<i>Đi theo</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (follow pace) ∧ (accompany)]]
<i>Chạy cùng</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (equal pace) ∧ (joint action)]]
<i>Nói đuôi</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (sequential pace) ∧ (follow in line)]]
<i>Sánh đôi</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(leg-based) ∧ (equal pace) ∧ (pair up)]]

The V_[M+CO] external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Truyện người hàng xóm* (Nam Cao).

- (18) Ngã để bà ấy cho **đi theo** đi bán hàng dăm.
 Ngã let lady that allow go follow go sell small goods
 ‘Ngã did it so that she would allow him to follow her to sell small wares.’

In this token, ⟨F⟩ is the understood follower, namely Ngã, who experiences displacement. The verb *đi* encodes MOVE(e) together with ⟨M⟩ as a neutral leg-based locomotion profile. The verb *theo* encodes ⟨CO⟩ by specifying that Ngã’s movement is aligned with *bà ấy* as a co-moving reference participant, that is, Ngã moves in accompaniment and in her trajectory. Consequently, this example sheds light on the properties of this pattern because an external manner-motion event is construed as coordinated motion between the ⟨F⟩ and another participant, and the co-motion component refines the event as following instead of independent displacement.

In short, the two-component external conflation patterns of Vietnamese manner-motion verbs show a core-periphery organization, in which the verb root encodes the manner-motion elements and peripheral lexical units add distinct co-event components. This result supports Talmy’s (2000) lexicalization framework because Vietnamese preserves a division between a manner-motion core and external enrichments. At the same time, these analyses argue against Talmy’s strict satellite-framed and verb-framed split since Vietnamese peripherals are not limited to particles or prepositions but they are often realized as ideophones, adverbs, or co-verbs that remain independent yet semantically co-equal with the manner-motion verb. In this respect, Vietnamese is typologically close to equipollently-framed languages such as Thai and Chinese, where serial verb constructions allow multiple semantic elements to share one clause without subordination, although Vietnamese differs from Chinese in that it generally avoids morphological compounding and instead keeps the components separable for flexible stacking. Vietnamese also differs from satellite-framed English, where similar meanings are usually optional adverbials or prepositional phrases, and from verb-framed Romance languages such as Spanish and French, where manner is frequently backgrounded and path or endpoint is

lexicalized in the verb. Cross-linguistically, the sound pattern parallels ideophonic systems in Japanese, but Vietnamese stands out for the productivity of reduplication, while circumstance and co-motion resemble adverbial framing in English or Korean, but they are more tightly integrated as serial components in Vietnamese. Therefore, Vietnamese external two-component conflation exemplifies a core-compression with the strategy of peripheral-component conflation, in which a compact manner-motion element is enriched by modular but constructionally expected co-event components, a profile that refines motion typology and supports Slobin’s (2004) thinking-for-speaking account by showing how Vietnamese grammar promotes the foregrounding of sensory, pragmatic, and interactional details in motion descriptions.

3.3 *VERB* [*PATH MOTION*]

This section aims to explore the semantic conflation patterns of path-motion verbs in Vietnamese, in which these verbs denote the prominent semantic components of Path ⟨P⟩. In other words, this section aims to clarify how Vietnamese organizes path and other components in the motion events. Accordingly, the internal conflation patterns of path-motion verbs are cases, in which the components of Path ⟨P⟩, and Ground ⟨G⟩, are encoded in the verbs themselves, which enables the verb itself to evoke a relatively complete event structure. In contrast, the external conflation patterns of path-motion verbs are configurations, in which the path-motion verbs serve as the central verbs, but the motion events are expanded at the level of the verb phrase by peripheral semantic components, such as Circumstance ⟨C⟩, Result ⟨R⟩, or purpose ⟨Pr⟩, and these components are encoded by accompanying elements or by other verbs in serial verb constructions. Table 3 summarizes the internal and external conflation patterns of path-motion verbs, and it shows the distribution and the degree of productivity of each conflation type. These results provide a basis for drawing generalizations about the tendency to wrap Path meaning in Vietnamese and about the role of constructional extension mechanisms in the expression of motion.

Table 4: Semantic conflation patterns of path-motion verbs

Semantic components	Internal conflation patterns		External conflation patterns					
	Internal semantic components (Ground, Path)		External semantic components (Circumstance, Emotion, Location, Result, Purpose, Time)					
Conflation Patterns	Path +	Ground 3	Path +	Circumstance 195	Path +	Result 36	Path +	Purpose 16
Total	3		247					

3.3.1 *Internal conflation patterns of path-motion verbs*

This section deals with the internal conflation patterns of path-motion verbs in Vietnamese, which occur in one pattern: V [_{P+G}] with 3 patterns. In these patterns, the Path ⟨P⟩ is directly integrated into the lexical meaning of verb. This allows the expression of a complete trajectory without the need for extra syntactic elements, which allow Vietnamese speakers to be able to

keep a minimal syntactic form while they still preserve precise path representation. MOVE_(i) denotes internal motion, which refers to an inherent change in the figure’s location that is lexically integrated in the verb itself without requiring an external manner-motion verbs or additional syntactic markers. These patterns can be wrapped in the general formula below:

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{PATH MOTION}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{F MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [(\text{P}) \wedge (\text{Inter-coms})]]$$

The V_[P+G] pattern in Vietnamese is a relatively rare type that is attested in only three verbs: *cập bến* (to dock), *hạ cánh* (to land), and *ra khơi* (to sail out to open sea). What is distinctive about this group is that each verb simultaneously integrates two internal semantic components inside a verb root, namely a ⟨P⟩ and a ⟨G⟩. Because ⟨P⟩ and ⟨G⟩ are co-lexicalized, the verb itself specifies both the inherent direction of motion and the landmark that anchors the event, so speakers can express a complete internal motion event without adding a separate locative complement. The generalized formula is:

$$V_{[\text{P}+\text{G}]} \Leftrightarrow [\text{F MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [(\text{P}) \wedge (\text{G})]]$$

In this structure, MOVE_(i) denotes an event of internal motion, that is, self-initiated displacement of the ⟨F⟩ instead of motion caused by an external agent. The ⟨P⟩ functions as a directional value encoded in the verb, such as inward approach, downward descent, or outward departure. The ⟨G⟩ functions as a ground landmark encoded in the verb, and this landmark is conceptually presupposed as the spatial anchor that is required for interpreting the trajectory. Concretely, *cập bến* encodes ⟨G⟩ as *bến* ‘dock or harbor’, *hạ cánh* encodes ⟨G⟩ as a landing ground, canonically a runway, and *ra khơi* encodes ⟨G⟩ as *khơi* (open sea).

<i>Cập bến</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{F MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [(\text{in water}) \wedge (\text{inward}) \wedge (\text{dock})]]$
<i>Hạ cánh</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{F MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [(\text{in air}) \wedge (\text{downward}) \wedge (\text{landing site})]]$
<i>Ra khơi</i>	$\Leftrightarrow [\text{F MOVE}_{(i)} \wedge [(\text{in water}) \wedge (\text{outward}) \wedge (\text{open sea})]]$

The V_[P+G] internal conflation pattern is illustrated in the following token from *Thi Đại Học Toàn Cầu* (Mộc Tô Lý).

- (19) Một khi đã ra khơi.
once already exit open-sea
‘Once (one) has set sail for the open sea.’

⟨F⟩ in this example is the understood sailing participant, which is subjected to internal motion. The verb *ra khơi* reflects V_[P+G] because it encodes ⟨P⟩ as an outward trajectory away from shore and it encodes ⟨G⟩ as the open sea ground landmark that anchors the motion. Therefore, the token realizes a internal motion event, in which ⟨F⟩ moves outward relative to a presupposed open-sea ground.

In short, the internal conflation pattern V_[P+G] in Vietnamese provides a compact, but it reveals test case for theories of motion lexicalization. First, the pattern is consistent with Talmy’s (2000) claim that some languages lexicalize path inside the verb because verbs such as *cập bến*, *hạ cánh*, and *ra khơi* encode an inherent ⟨P⟩ together with a ⟨G⟩, which allow a trajectory without an overt locative complement. This property makes Vietnamese comparable

to verb-framed systems such as Spanish or French, where path is frequently internal to the verb, and it also resembles lexical classes in English that incorporate goal-ground meaning (for example *dock* or *land*), even though English overall prefers satellites. However, the Vietnamese pattern indicates that path-framing can coexist with an equipollent architecture in the language. Vietnamese does not build path meaning via morphological root expansion or resultative compounding as in Chinese, nor does it depend on obligatory satellites as in English. Instead, it achieves path-ground completeness through monomorphemic verbs whose lexical semantics already integrate both the motion and path components. Therefore, the rarity of $V_{[P+G]}$ matters typologically because it reveals that Vietnamese path verbs are not a framing system on their own, but a specialized lexical niche that compresses trajectory and landmark for maximal economy and precision. In short, Vietnamese internal path-motion verbs refine motion typology by revealing a lexical-niche strategy: even in a language that extensively exploits serial constructions, a small class of verbs can still encode $\langle P \rangle$ and $\langle G \rangle$ internally that forms self-sufficient internal-motion events. This supports event-structure models, in which ground information may be part of verb meaning rather than peripheral.

3.3.2 External conflation patterns of path-motion verbs

This section addresses the external conflation patterns of Vietnamese path-motion verbs, which are attested in four constructions: $V_{[P+C]}$ (195), $V_{[P+R]}$ (36), and $V_{[P+Pr]}$ (16), which produce 247 patterns in total. Across these patterns, the main verb preserves a compact core that encodes MOVE(e), an external motion event whose semantic nucleus profiles motion together with an inherent path value, while the external component contributes an additional discourse-semantic component as an independent unit, such as an adverb, a secondary verb, or a second verb. Among the four types, $V_{[P+C]}$ is by far the most frequent because it offers the most flexible and economical expansion of a motion-path element, in which this pattern preserves the path-motion verb and adds circumstance as a peripheral component that is syntactically co-equal with the verb in serial constructions. Circumstance is also the most accessible component in natural discourse, since it readily encodes speaker evaluation, situational setting, or pragmatic stance without requiring subordination, so $V_{[P+C]}$ functions as a default option in motion description. By contrast, $V_{[P+R]}$ introduces more specific components, namely a result endpoint, and therefore occur only when those meanings are discourse-relevant. $V_{[P+Pr]}$ is the least frequent because it combines two different external components in one construction, namely a Path $\langle P \rangle$ and a Purpose $\langle Pr \rangle$. The general schema is:

$$\text{VERB}_{[\text{PATH MOTION}]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle P \rangle \wedge \langle \text{Exter-coms} \rangle]]$$

The $V_{[P+C]}$ pattern is an external conflation type of Vietnamese path-motion verbs that is canonically realized as a verb phrase consisting of a path verb followed by an adverbial element. In this pattern, the main verb encodes MOVE(e) together with an inherent Path component $\langle P \rangle$, while the following adverbial unit contributes an external Circumstance component $\langle C \rangle$, which can be temporal, locative, psychological, situational, or evaluative. The general formula is:

$$V_{[P+C]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle P \rangle \wedge \langle \text{Circumstance} \rangle]]$$

In this pattern, ⟨F⟩ experiences displacement, MOVE(e) designates an external motion event, and ⟨P⟩ is a non-neutral path value that is fixed by the verb root itself, such as inward entry (*vào*), outward exit (*ra*), or upward movement (*lên*). The ⟨C⟩ is contributed outside the verb root as an adverbial component. This component does not supply a second path, and it does not change the argument structure of verb. Instead, it refines the same path event by anchoring it to a contextual parameter that is conceptually independent from the trajectory but interpretively inseparable from the event in discourse. In other words, the verb supplies the directional element of displacement, whereas the adverb specifies the conditions under which that displacement is carried out, for example quiet manner, hurried pace, leisurely attitude, temporal sequence, or situational staging. This division of labor explains why V_[P + C] is highly productive in Vietnamese, in which the path-motion verb keeps the motion core compact, and the adverbial circumstance provides immediate experiential or discourse framing without resorting to subordination. Typical verb phrases include *vào lặng lẽ* ‘to enter quietly’, *ra vội vàng* ‘to go out hurriedly’, and *lên thong thả* ‘to go up leisurely’, in which ⟨P⟩ is inherent to the verb and ⟨C⟩ is a contextual component added by the adverb.

<i>Vào lặng lẽ</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(inward) ∧ ⟨quietly⟩]]
<i>Ra vội vàng</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(outward) ∧ ⟨hurriedly⟩]]
<i>Lên thong thả</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(upward) ∧ ⟨leisurely⟩]]
<i>Vào sau</i>	⇔ [F MOVE _(e) ∧ [(inward) ∧ ⟨later/afterwards⟩]]

The V_[P + C] external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Truyện người hàng xóm* (Nam Cao).

- (20) Một bọn ba bốn người **vào sau**.
 one group three four person enter after
 ‘A group of three or four people entered afterwards.’

In this example, ⟨F⟩ is *một bọn ba bốn người* that is displaced. The verb *vào* encodes MOVE(e) with ⟨P⟩ as an inward path of entry. The adverb *sau* encodes ⟨C⟩ as a temporal circumstance of succession that indicates that the entry event is ordered after a salient prior event or group. Consequently, the verb phrase Verb + adverb illustrates a path-motion element expanded by one circumstance component, exactly as specified by V_[P + C] ⇔ [F MOVE_(e) ∧ [(P) ∧ ⟨Circumstance⟩]] because the inward trajectory is provided by the verb root and the temporal sequencing is provided by the adverbial circumstance.

The V_[P + R] pattern is an external conflation type of Vietnamese path-motion verbs that is canonically realized as a verb phrase consisting of a path verb followed by a noun. In this pattern, the ⟨P⟩ is integrated into the main verb, and the following noun contributes an ⟨R⟩ that specifies the attained outcome of the motion-path event. The general formula is:

$$V_{[P + R]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [(P) \wedge \langle \text{Result} \rangle]]$$

This group of V_[P + R] path-motion verbs can be characterized as path-verb-noun complexes, in which the verb root encodes ⟨P⟩ and the noun encodes ⟨R⟩ as the telic endpoint. Verb phrases such as *vào biên chế* ‘to enter official employment’, *ra đời* ‘to come into existence’, and *lên chức* ‘to rise in position’ exemplify this pattern because *vào*, *ra*, and *lên* encode inward,

outward, and upward path values while *biên chế*, *đời*, and *chức* encode the attained employment status, existence-state, and promoted rank. Consequently, these constructions differ from path-motion verbs because the result is not optional, but it is stated by the noun component that completes the macro-event.

<i>Vào biên chế</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(inward) \wedge (become officially employed)]]
<i>Ra đời</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(outward) \wedge (be born)]]
<i>Lên chức</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(upward) \wedge (promoted)]]

The V_[P+R] external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Đời thừa* (Nam Cao).

- (21) Lúc đứa con ra đời
when one child exit life
‘When the child was born’

The ⟨F⟩ is *đứa con*, whose displacement is construed as emergence into existence. The verb *ra* encodes MOVE_(e) with ⟨P⟩ as an outward path of emergence. The noun *đời* encodes ⟨R⟩ as the resultant existence-state of being born. Therefore, the verb phrase Verb + Noun describes V_[P+R] \Leftrightarrow [F MOVE_(e) \wedge [(P) \wedge (Result)]], because the path element is supplied by the verb and the achieved result is supplied by the noun.

The V_[P+Pr] pattern is an external conflation type of Vietnamese path-motion verbs that is typically realized as a verb phrase that consists of a path verb followed by a purpose verb or goal-oriented verb. In this pattern, the first verb encodes a Path component ⟨P⟩ that profiles the direction of displacement, and the second element encodes a Purpose or goal-action component ⟨Pr⟩ that motivates the displacement and specifies what activity the motion is directed toward. The general formula is:

$$V_{[P+Pr]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [(P) \wedge (Pr)]]$$

In this structure, ⟨F⟩ undergoes displacement, MOVE_(e) denotes an external motion event, ⟨P⟩ is the inherent path value contributed by the path verb, and ⟨Pr⟩ is the goal-oriented event contributed by the following predicate. The two components remain syntactically independent in a serial construction, but they are interpreted as one coherent macro event because they share the same ⟨F⟩ and because ⟨Pr⟩ provides the purposive endpoint that renders the path motion goal-directed rather than direction-only.

<i>Ra tòa</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(outward) \wedge (testify)]]
<i>Đi học</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(toward school) \wedge (study)]]
<i>Đi chợ</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(toward market) \wedge (buy goods)]]
<i>Về quê</i>	\Leftrightarrow [F MOVE _(e) \wedge [(homeward) \wedge (return to hometown)]]

This group of V_[P+Pr] path-motion verbs can be characterized as serial complexes, in which a directionally specified path verb anchors the displacement nucleus, and a following purpose predicate anchors the intended endpoint-action. Verb phrases such as *ra tòa* ‘to go to court’, *đi học* ‘to go to school’, *đi chợ* ‘to go to the market’, and *về quê* ‘to return to the hometown’

exemplify this pattern because the path verbs *ra*, *đi*, and *về* encode ⟨P⟩ as outward movement, directed going, or homeward return, while the complements *tò*, *học*, *chợ*, and *quê* encode ⟨Pr⟩ as the goal action or socially defined activity associated with that destination. Therefore, these verb phrases differ from path-motion verbs that only encode trajectory because the second element is not an optional locative supplement, but a purposive component that completes the interpretation of the motion as oriented toward a goal event. The $V_{[P+Pr]}$ external conflation is illustrated in the following token from *Sao lại thế này* (Nam Cao).

- (22) Nghi hè cũng không dám về quê.
holiday summer also not dare return hometown
‘Even during the summer break, (he) did not dare to return to his hometown.’

In this example, ⟨F⟩ is the understood subject who would be the returning participant. The verb *về* encodes $MOVE_{(e)}$ together with ⟨P⟩ as a homeward path of return. The noun *quê* encodes ⟨Pr⟩ as the goal-oriented endpoint that defines the intended return event, namely reaching and re-entering the socially salient homeland domain. The modal sequence *không dám* negates the realization of the macro event, but it does not change the internal organization of the pattern. Consequently, the phrase *về quê* instantiates $V_{[P+Pr]} \Leftrightarrow [F \text{ MOVE}_{(e)} \wedge [\langle P \rangle \wedge \langle Pr \rangle]]$ because the path element is supplied by the verb root and the purposive goal component is supplied by the following verb that produces a goal-directed path-motion event.

In short, the three patterns confirm that Vietnamese path-motion verbs employ a core-periphery organization: the verb root anchors $MOVE_{(e)}$ and an inherent path value ⟨P⟩, while a second unit adds a distinct external component. This organization is broadly consistent with Talmy’s framework because circumstantial adverbs in $V_{[P+C]}$ and result nouns in $V_{[P+R]}$ function like satellites in the sense that they supply endpoint or contextual information outside the verb. At the same time, $V_{[P+Pr]}$ aligns with equipollent systems such as Thai and Chinese, since purpose is encoded by a co-verb that remains syntactically independent but forms one macro-event with the path-motion verb. However, Vietnamese does not fit neatly into a typological type. It differs from Spanish and French, where purpose and many results are typically expressed through subordinated or prepositional structures, not as co-equal components in the same verb phrase. It also differs from English because the external component is not restricted to particles or prepositions but can be realized as adverbs, nouns, or full co-verbs. Finally, it diverges from Chinese resultative compounding because Vietnamese components are phrasal and separable rather than morphologically fused. In short, Vietnamese combines verb-internal path anchoring with construction-level componenting, which gives rise to a stable intermediate strategy that expands event meaning without changing verbal morphology.

4 Conclusion

This study has systematically identified and classified the semantic conflation patterns of Vietnamese motion verbs through Talmy’s (1985, 2000) lexicalization patterns, Slobin’s (2004) thinking-for-speaking hypothesis, Goldberg’s (1995) construction grammar, and Levin and Rappaport Hovav’s (1995, 1998, 2010) event-structure approach as its analytical

foundations. The findings reveal a typologically hybrid system. A particularly revealing result is that Vietnamese achieves high telic density in caused-motion without morphological compounding, instead of relying on productive constructional componenting (e.g. V_1 + Result/ State/ Direction). This supports an independent typological parameter of endpoint-externalization, beyond the classic verb and satellite-framed split. In this study, hybrid encoding strategy refers to the stable coexistence of multiple motion-packaging options in Vietnamese. Internal conflation patterns show that Vietnamese can lexicalize core components such as Manner, Path, and Cause, and in some patterns Figure and Ground, directly in the verb root, so that the motion element is compact and self-contained. External conflation patterns show that Vietnamese systematically expands this core through constructional componenting, in which peripheral components such as Direction, Result, Circumstance, Purpose, Vehicle, Sound, and Time are realized as serial verbs, secondary predicates, particles, or adverbial units. Vietnamese further employs equipollent serial-verb constructions that distribute Manner and Path across co-equal verbs. Therefore, hybridity here denotes a consistent typological profile that combines verb-root packaging with construction-level componenting.

From a theoretical perspective, Vietnamese refines Talmy's typology by demonstrating a structural pathway through which verb-framed and equipollently-framed strategies can operate in one language, even though they are often treated as distinct types in cross-linguistic accounts. The patterns also substantiate Slobin's claim that grammatical affordances shape conceptualization because Vietnamese speakers recurrently encode a core motion event first and then add peripheral components to increase descriptive precision and discourse richness. In addition, treating these recurrent form-meaning pairings as constructions supports Goldberg's view that constructions themselves are meaning-bearing units capable of hosting both core and peripheral semantic components without requiring morphological alteration of the verb. Finally, the Vietnamese patterns extend event-structure models by showing that Figure and Ground can be lexically presupposed inside the verb root, and that peripheral components can contribute independent event meanings while remaining integrated into a single macro-event representation.

In practical terms, the results are relevant for second-language teaching, translation, and natural language processing. For pedagogy, recognizing the hybrid encoding strategy allows teaching materials to guide learners from different backgrounds in mapping motion components onto Vietnamese verb roots and serial constructions, which reduces cross-linguistic interference. For translation, the findings show that equivalence requires attention to how Vietnamese distributes core motion meaning and peripheral components, so that semantic nuance and structural fidelity are preserved. For computational applications, the classification of conflation patterns offers a structured resource for semantic parsing and machine translation that is sensitive to cross-linguistic variation in event packaging. The study is limited to dictionary entries and a selected narrative data, so colloquial and dialectal variation may be underrepresented. Future research should expand the dataset to spoken discourse, experimental elicitation, and systematic comparison with other Southeast Asian languages. Overall, the study contributes empirical evidence and analytical refinement to motion-event typology by clarifying how Vietnamese balances semantic compression with contextual elaboration in a hybrid system.

References

- Aske, Jon. 1989. Path predicates in English and Spanish: A closer look. *Proceedings of the Fifteenth Annual Meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society* 15. 1–14.
- Beavers, John & Levin, Beth & Tham, Shiao Wei. 2010. The typology of motion expressions revisited. *Journal of Linguistics* 46(2). 331–377.
- Bohnemeyer, Jürgen & Danziger, Eve & Lum, Jonathon & Alshehri, Ali & Benedicto, Elena & Blythe, Joe & Cerqueglini, Letizia & Donelson, Katharine & Eggleston, Alyson & Gaby, Alice & Lin, Yen-Ting & Moore, Randi & Nikitina, Tatiana & Stoakes, Hywel & Balna, Mayangna Yulbarangyang. 2022. Reference frames in language and cognition: Cross-population mismatches. *Linguistics Vanguard* 8(s1). 175–189.
- Cadierno, Teresa. 2017. Thinking-for-speaking about motion in a second language: Looking back and forward. In Ibarretxe-Antuñano, Iraide (ed.), *Motion and space across languages: Theory and applications*, 279–300. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Chen, Liang & Guo, Jiansheng. 2009. Motion events in Chinese novels: Evidence for an equipollently-framed language. *Journal of Pragmatics* 41. 1749–1766.
- Dong, Sicong & Ding, Hongdi. 2025. A typological study of rainfall expressions in Sino-Tibetan languages. *Studies in Language* 50 (1).68-108.
- Dương, Hữu Biên. 2023. Vietnamese fictive motion constructions: A construction grammar approach. *Cogent Arts & Humanities* 10(1). 2156671.
- Essegbey, James & Thomas, Givon, Larry M, Hyman & Thomas, Hinnebusch.2021. Reminiscences of the last 50 years and the way forward. *Studies in African Linguistics* 50(1). 2–7.
- Fagard, Benjamin & Zlatev, Jordan & Kopecka, Anetta & Cerruti, Massimo & Blomberg, Johan. 2013. The expression of motion events: A quantitative study of six typologically varied languages. *Proceedings of the 39th Annual Meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society*. 364–379.
- Goldberg, Adele E. 1995. *Constructions: A construction grammar approach to argument structure*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Goldberg, Adele E. 2006. *Constructions at work: The nature of generalization in language*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Hoàng, Phê. 2020. *Vietnamese dictionary*. Thanh Hóa: Nhà xuất bản Hồng Đức.
- Hoàng, Tuyết Minh. 2016. Path verbs in Vietnamese. *Language & Life* 1(243). 2–6.
- Ibarretxe-Antuñano, Iraide. 2025. The use of Basque ideophones in motion events. *Cognitive Semantics* 11(2). 1–27.
- Lai Nguyen.2001. *Directional motion words in modern Vietnamese*. Hanoi: Social Sciences Publishing House.
- Lakoff, George & Johnson, Mark. 1980. *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

- Levin, Beth & Rappaport Hovav, Malka. 1995. *Unaccusativity: At the syntax-lexical semantics interface*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Levin, Beth & Rappaport Hovav, Malka. 1998. Building verb meanings. In Butt, Miriam & Geuder, Wilhelm (eds.), *The projection of arguments: Lexical and compositional factors*, 97–134. Stanford: CSLI Publications.
- Levin, Beth & Rappaport Hovav, Malka. 2010. Reflections on manner/result complementarity. In Rappaport Hovav, Malka & Doron, Edit & Sichel, Ivy (eds.), *Lexical semantics, syntax, and event structure*, 21–38. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Luu, Quy Khuong & Lý, Ngọc Toàn. 2018. The lexicalization patterns of manner motion events in Vietnamese. *English Linguistics Research* 7(4). 1–14.
- Lý, Ngọc Toàn. 2019. Lexical expressions of path motion in Vietnamese: A perspective from cognitive linguistics. *International Journal of Language and Literary Studies* 1(1). 14–20.
- Lý, Ngọc Toàn. 2022. Expressions of caused motion in Vietnamese: A perspective from cognitive linguistics. *Journal of the Southeast Asian Linguistics Society* 15(1). 51–78.
- Mai, Thi Thu Han. 2011. Verbs of motion and their lexicalization patterns in English and Vietnamese: A perspective from cognitive semantics. *VNU Journal of Science: Foreign Languages* 27. 107–114.
- Naigles, Letitia R. & Eisenberg, Ann R. & Kako, Edward T. & Highter, Melissa & McGraw, Nancy. 1998. Speaking of motion: Verb use in English and Spanish. *Language and Cognitive Processes* 13(5). 521–549.
- Quang, Hùng & Khắc, Lâm. 2007. *Vietnamese dictionary*. Hanoi: Encyclopedia Dictionary Publisher.
- Slobin, Dan I. 2004. The many ways to search for a frog: Linguistic typology and the expression of motion events. In Strömquist, Sven & Verhoeven, Ludo (eds.), *Relating events in narrative, volume 2: Typological and contextual perspectives*, 219–257. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Talmy, Leonard. 1985. Lexicalization patterns: Semantic structure in lexical forms. In Shopen, Timothy (ed.), *Language typology and syntactic description 3: Grammatical categories and the lexicon*, 57–149. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Talmy, Leonard. 2000. *Toward a cognitive semantics II: Typology and process in concept structuring*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Van Hoey, Thomas. 2025. Waddling, wandering and waving: Literary Chinese ideophones and the motion semantic grid. *Cognitive Semantics* 11. 1–29.
- Võ, Tú Phương. 2025. Motion verbs in Vietnamese and English. *Ensino em Perspectivas* 6(1). 1–23.
- Zlatev, Jordan & Yangklang, Peerapat. 2004. A third way to travel: The place of Thai in motion event typology. In Strömquist, Sven & Verhoeven, Ludo (eds.), *Relating events in narrative, volume*

2: *Typological and contextual perspectives*, 159–190. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.

Appendix A

SHORT STORIES USED IN THE CORPUS

1. Nam Cao (1941). Chí Phèo. <https://book.sachgiai.com>
2. Nam Cao (1937). Ngèo. <https://www.sachhayonline.com>
3. Nam Cao (1937). Đui Mù. <https://www.sachhayonline.com>
4. Nam Cao (1940). Cái Chết Của Con Mực. <https://www.sachhayonline.com>
5. Nguyễn Trung Thành (1965). Rừng Xà Nu. <https://download.vn>
6. Nam Cao (1945). Trên những con đường Việt Bắc.
7. Nam Cao. Điều vãn. <https://www.sachhayonline.com>
8. Hoắc Hương Cô (n.d.). Mỹ Nhân Nhập Vai. Retrieved from <http://truyenfull.vn>
9. Nghiêm Diệu Linh (n.d.). Đồng Trinh Ngải. Retrieved from <https://sachmoi.net>
10. Nam Cao. Trần Cừ. www.sachvui.com
11. Nam Cao (1943). Mua nhà. <https://www.sachhayonline.com>
12. Nam Cao (1943). Nước mắt. <https://isach.info>
13. Nam Cao (1943). Đòi thừa. www.sachvui.com
14. Nam Cao (1943). Sao lại thế này. www.sachvui.com
15. Nam Cao (1944). Truyện người hàng xóm. www.sachvui.com
16. Ngọc Tấn (2025). Người làng Ner. <https://baovannghe.vn>
17. Mộc Tô Lý (2019). Thi Đại Học Toàn Cầu. Retrieved from <http://truyenfull.vn>

Appendix B

CAUSE VERBS (INTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	Internal conflation patterns (Cause, Motion, Manner, Path)		
Semantic conflation patterns	Cause + Figure + Motion	Cause + Motion + Manner	Cause + Motion + Path
Causative verbs	Bắn Bấm Bom Đâm Lao Phà Rạch Vắt	Bật Bỏ Búng Đá Đập Ép Giật Húc Khiêng Khuấy	Án Cắm Chát Chèn Chêm Dí Đẩy Đè Đồ Ép

		Lắc Lăn Lông Mang Ném Rắc Rung Thối Quăng Quảng Rắc Rải Tung Vác Xê dịch Xoay Xô	Hạ Hắt Hút Kéo Lao Lôi Nạp Nâng Nén Nhắc Nhét Nhỏ Nhồi Phóng Phun Quật Tách Thả Vung Vốt
Total	8	27	30

CAUSE VERBS (EXTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	External conflation patterns (Cause, Motion, Change, Result, State, Volume)					
	Cause + Motion + Result	Cause + Motion + Result + Manner	Cause + Motion + Result + Direction	Cause + Motion + Change	Cause + Motion + State	Cause + Motion + Volume
Causative verbs	Bắn hạ Bắn roi Bắn thun Bắn văng Bè cong Bè gãy Bóp nát Bứt rời Cán bẹp Cán nát Cào đồ Cào nát Cuốn phẫ Cuốn trôi Đập đồ Đập gãy Đầm nát Đập bẹp Đập nát Đập vỡ Đề bẹp Đề dẹt Đẩy bật Đẩy lùi Đẩy ngã Đẩy sập Ép phẳng	Đẩy ngã nhào Đẩy ngã lăn Kéo đồ âm Kéo sập âm âm Hắt tung mạnh Hắt văng ra xa Húc văng ra ngoài Giật tung mạnh Giật đồ ập xuống Xô đồ nhào Xô sập mạnh Lôi tuột ra ngoài Đập vỡ tan Đập nát bầy Đề bẹp dí Ném vỡ tan tàn Quật ngã gục xuống Quật tung lên cao	Hắt văng ra Hắt văng vào Hắt tung lên t Hắt rơi xuống Hắt rơi xuống Húc văng ra Húc đồ xuống Húc đồ ra Giật tuột khỏi Giật đồ xuống Giật đồ xuống Giật sập xuống Xô đồ xuống Xô đồ xuống Xô lệch sang Xô ngã ra Xô ngã vào Xô ngã ra Quật ngã xuống Quật đồ ra Quật đồ xuống Quật ngã ra Quật văng ra Quăng nát vào	Bè cong Bè thẳng Bóp dẹp Bóp méo Cán bẹp Cán dẹt Cán mỏng Cán phẳng Cuộn tròn Cuộn lại Đề bẹp Đề bẹt Đập bẹt Đập bẹp Ép bẹt Ép dẹp Ép phẳng Ép thẳng Ép xẹp Kéo cong Kéo dẫn Kéo thẳng Kéo to ra Kéo lệch Mở rộng Nắn cong	Buộc chặt Cuộn chặt Đề cứng ngắc Đóng ghi Đóng kín Ép chặt Ép dính Ép sát Gập gọn Gập gọn Kẹp chặt Kẹp cứng Khép chặt Khép kín Mở toang Nén chặt Siết chặt Siết cố định Siết cứng Thắt chặt	Bom căng Bom phồng Kéo căng Kéo dẫn Mở bung Nới bung Thối căng Thối phồng

	Ép vụn Giật đồ Giật gãy Giật phẫn Giật tung Ha gục Hắt đồ Hắt rơi Hắt tung Húc đồ Húc ngã Húc văng Kéo bung Kéo đồ Kéo nghiêng Kéo sập Lật đồ Lật úp Ném vỡ Quật gãy Quật ngã Quật đồ Rạch toạc Uốn cong Vặn gãy Xé rách Xé toạc Xô đồ Xô lệch Xô ngã Xô sập Úi sập	Xúc đồ ào ào Hắt rơi xuống đất	Quăng vỡ xuống Quăng vỡ xuống Ném vỡ xuống Ném vỡ xuống Ném vỡ ra Ném bay ra Ném tung lên Lôi tuột ra n Lôi tuột xuống Lôi tuột ra Kéo sập xuống Kéo sập xuống Kéo đồ ra ngoài Kéo nghiêng sang Kéo bật ra Đẩy bật ra Đẩy bật ra Đẩy lệch sang Đẩy lùi về Đẩy ngã ra Đập vỡ bay xuống Đập vỡ văng ra Đập gãy rơi xuống Đập nát bay ra Ép bật ra	Nấn méo Nấn thẳng Nấn tròn Nới bung Nới rộng Siết lại Thối phồng Uốn cong Uốn thẳng Vặn cong Vặn lệch Vặn méo Vặn thẳng Xòe rộng Xòe to Xoay lệch Xoay nghiêng		
Total	59	20	49	44	20	8

MANNER VERBS (INTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	Internal conflation patterns		
	Internal components (Figure, Ground, Manner, Motion)		
Conflation patterns of manner verbs	Motion + Manner	Motion + Manner + Figure	Motion + Manner + Ground
	Bật Bén mảng Biến Bò Cắt cánh Chạy Chìm Chòm Cút đi Dao động Dạo	Banh Bệt Bước Chành Chìa Choài Cúi Dậm Duỗi Gật Giang	Bay Bơi Cập bến Chui Đạt Đậu Hạ cánh Lấn Lội Lượn Tràn

	Dập dờn Đắm Di chuyển Điều hành Dao động Dập dờn Đắm Đung đưa Gục Hụp Lan Lách Lánh Lảo đảo Lắc lư Len Lê Lét Lộn Lướt Lúi Nhảy Rào bức Rẽ Roi Rũ Sà Sập Sụt Trào Trườn Trượt Tuôn Tuột Vẩy tay Vọt Vung	Dang Khom Mưa Ngảng Run Toài Uỡn Vươn	Trèo
Total	45	19	12
		76	

MANNER VERBS (EXTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	External conflation patterns				
	External components (Circumstance, Sound, Trajectory, Vehicle)				
	Motion + Manner + Sound	Motion + Manner + Circumstance	Motion + Manner + Purpose	Motion + Manner + Vehicle	Motion + Manner + Co-motion
Conflation patterns of manner verbs	Bay phành phạch Bay vèo Bay vù vù Bò sột xoạt Chạy cồm cộp Chạy rầm rập Chạy thình thịch Đi lạch bạch Đi lộp cộp Đi lẹp xẹp Đi loẹt quẹt	Bay bông Bay nhảy Chạy bần Chạy tung tang Đi chập chững Đi khệnh khạng Đi loanh quanh Đi lòng vòng Đi lạch Đi lang thang Đi lững thững	Chạy chợ Chạy trốn Chạy chữa Chạy vốn Chạy quảng cáo Chạy giao hàng Chạy dịch Đi chợ Đi chùa Đi học Đi câu	Bay máy bay Chạy tàu thủy Chèo nghe Chèo thuyền Chèo xuống Cưỡi ngựa Cưỡi trâu Cưỡi voi Đi ca nô Đi cà kheo Đi phà	Bám theo Bám sát Chạy cùng Chạy đồng hành Chạy lẻo đẻo Chạy sát bên Chạy theo Đẫn theo Đắt theo Đí theo Đi cùng

	Đi phịch phịch Lăn lóc cóc Kéo sột soạt Lao vun vút Lôi rầm rập Ném phịch Ngã ụych Nhảy bộp Roi loảng xoảng Roi lách tách Roi lộp bộp Roi ào ào Roi leng keng Roi rào rào Roi tí tách Roi bịch bịch Quăng bộp	Đi rón rén Đi thơ thần Đi vội vã Đi gập gáp Đi khập khiễng Đi khúm núm Nhảy non ton Nhảy xa	Đi làm Đi du lịch Đi hành hương Đi giao lưu Đi vận động Đi sơ tán Đi lễ Đi tập thể dục Đi săn Đi xin việc	Đi taxi Đi xe buýt Đi thuyền Lái xe Lướt ván Trượt ván	Đi kèm Đi theo Nối đuôi Sánh đôi
Total	28	19	21	17	15
	100				

PATH VERBS (INTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	Internal semantic components (Ground, Motion, Path)	
	Motion + Path	Motion + Path + Ground
Conflation patterns of path verbs	Đến Lên Lùi Xuống Vào Về Ra Rút lui Tới Lại Tiến Trở lại Quay về	Cập bến Hạ cánh Ra khơi
Total	13	3
	16	

PATH VERBS (EXTERNAL CONFLATION PATTERNS)

Semantic components	External semantic components (Circumstance, Emotion, Location, Result, Purpose, Time)			
	Motion + Path + Circumstance	Motion + Path + Result	Motion + Path + Time	Motion + Path + Purpose
Conflation patterns of path verbs	Đến dần Đến chậm Đến gấp Đến hạn	Đến đích Lên đỉnh Lên chức Lên giá	Đến trễ Đến đúng giờ Đến kịp Đến lâu	Đi học Đi chợ Đi chùa Đi viện

Đến ngay	Lên lớp	Đến liền	Đi làm
Đến nhanh	Lên ngôi	Đến muộn	Đi lễ
Đến liền lập tức	Lên hạng	Đến sớm	Đi cầu
Đến đều đặn	Lên sàn	Đến trễ	Đi chơi
Đến liên tục	Lên sóng	Vào đúng giờ	Đi họp
Đến ngay lập tức	Lên tiếng	Vào kịp	Đi sản
Đến tạm thời	Lên truyền hình	Vào lâu	Đi bơi
Đi hồi hả	Lên bục vinh quang	Vào liền	Vào viện
Đến tức thì	Tới đích	Vào muộn	Đến trường
Lên đều đặn	Vào biên chế	Vào sớm	Ra viện
Lùi chậm rãi	Vào đảng	Vào trễ	Về nước
Ra ào ào	Vào khuôn khổ	Ra chậm	Về quê
Lên chậm	Vào nếp	Ra đúng giờ	
Lên từ từ	Vào giường	Ra kịp	
Lên dần	Vào số đen	Ra lâu	
Lên gấp	Vào thể trận	Ra muộn	
Lên nhất thời	Vào thị trường	Ra nhanh	
Lên lâu	Vào vòng chung kết	Ra sớm	
Lên liền	Về đích	Ra trễ	
Lên nhanh	Về hưu	Rút lui đúng giờ	
Lên liền lập tức	Ra đề	Rút lui kịp	
Lên liên tục	Ra quân	Rút lui muộn	
Lên ngay	Ra đời	Rút lui sớm	
Lên ngay lập tức	Ra trường	Rút lui trễ	
Lên tạm thời	Ra tòa	Trở lại đúng giờ	
Lên tức thì	Ra khỏi tổ chức	Trở lại kịp	
Ra đều đặn	Ra khỏi danh sách	Trở lại lâu	
Ra ngay	Rút lui khỏi chính trường	Trở lại muộn	
Ra dần	Trở lại ghế nóng	Trở lại sớm	
Ra gấp	Xuống báng xếp hạng	Trở lại trễ	
Ra liền	Xuống chức	Tới chậm	
Ra liền lập tức	Xuống cấp	Tới đúng giờ	
Ra ngay lập tức	Xuống sức	Tới kịp	
Ra nhất thời		Tới lâu	
Ra vĩnh viễn		Tới muộn	
Ra liên tục		Tới sớm	
Ra tạm thời		Tới trễ	
Ra tức thì		Tiến lên đúng giờ	
Rút lui nhất thời		Tiến lên kịp	
Rút lui tạm thời		Tiến lên lâu	
Rút lui ngay		Tiến lên liền	
Rút lui ngay lập tức		Tiến lên muộn	
Rút lui nhanh		Tiến lên sớm	
Rút lui dần		Tiến lên trễ	
Rút lui gấp		Về đúng giờ	
Rút lui liền		Về kịp	
Rút lui chậm		Về lâu	
Rút lui vĩnh viễn		Về liền	
Rút lui liên tục		Về muộn	
Rút lui tức thì		Về sớm	
Trở lại chậm		Về trễ	
Tiến dồn dập		Lên đúng giờ	
Tới dồn dập		Lên kịp	
Tới tức thì		Lên muộn	
Tới nhanh		Lên sớm	
Xuống rón rén		Lên trễ	
Vào chậm		Xuống đúng giờ	
Vào đều đặn		Xuống kịp	
Vào tạm thời		Xuống lâu	
Vào lạng lẽ		Xuống muộn	
Vào dần		Xuống sớm	

	<p>Vào gấp Vào liên tục Vào liên lập tức Vào tức thì Vào ngay Vào ngay lập tức Vào nhanh Về thông thả Về nhất thời Rút lui âm thầm Tiến lên chậm Tiến lên đều đặn Tiến lên dần Tiến lên liên lập tức Tiến lên ngay Tiến lên gấp Tiến lên ngay lập tức Tiến lên tạm thời Tiến lên tức thì Tiến lên nhất thời Tiến lên nhanh Tiến lên vĩnh viễn Tiến lên liên tục Trở lại liên tục Về chậm Về dần Về gấp Về ngay Về ngay lập tức Về nhanh Về liên tục Về tức thì Về tạm thời Về liên lập tức Về đều đặn Tới đều đặn Tới dần Tới gấp Tới liên Tới liên lập tức Tới liên tục Trở lại đều đặn Trở lại gấp Trở lại liên Trở lại liên lập tức Trở lại ngay Trở lại ngay lập tức Trở lại nhanh Trở lại nhất thời Trở lại vĩnh viễn Trở lại tạm thời Trở lại tức thì Xuống liên tục Xuống ngay Xuống ngay lập tức Xuống nhanh Xuống nhất thời Xuống tạm thời Xuống tức thì Xuống vĩnh viễn Xuống liên</p>		<p>Xuống trễ</p>	
--	--	--	------------------	--

	Xuống liền lập tức Xuống chậm Xuống đều đặn Xuống dần Xuống gấp			
Total	129	36	66	16
247				

Ly Ngoc Toan
Ho Chi Minh City University of Law
02 Nguyen Tat Thanh, Xom Chieu Ward
Ho Chi Minh City
Vietnam
e-mail: lntoan@hcmulaw.edu.vn

In SKASE Journal of Theoretical Linguistics [online]. 2026, vol. 23, no. 1 [cit. 2026-06-30]. Available on web page <http://www.skase.sk/Volumes/JTL61/06.pdf>. ISSN 1336-782X